

MAELSTROM

MArInE Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management

D2.2

Numerical modelling and field campaigns to support litter removal at the demo sites

31/03/2023

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General Information

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Executive Summary

Within the MAELSTROM project two complementary marine litter removal technologies are developed and tested. An automated seabed cleaning platform has been developed with a cable-robot able to remove marine litter from the seafloor at demo locations in the coastal area near Venice (Italy), and a Bubble Barrier system will be implemented to remove marine litter from the water column in the Ave estuary (Portugal). In order to select locations where the technologies can best be applied and to assess the impact of the litter removal on marine life, we have set-up and applied numerical models. Furthermore, results of field observations that were carried out in the framework of MAELSTROM are analysed and are put into context using the numerical modelling results.

For the coastal area near Venice, the transport and fate of marine macrolitter from three main source types was derived from particle tracking modelling, making use of hydrodynamic model results for the entire Adriatic Sea. The source input was estimated for marine litter from cities, from rivers and from aquaculture and fisheries. This approach was followed to estimate locations where marine litter accumulates on the seafloor. Such locations have a much higher litter density than average, and we refer to them as "hotspots". Despite the various uncertainties in the modelling methods, the resulting maps of the item density on the sea floor are coherent with the available literature and represent a first assessment on the distribution of marine macrolitter accumulation in this region. Potential hotspot maps were obtained for both the entire northern Adriatic Sea (Gulf of Venice) and for the area around the Venice Lagoon. At the large scale the potential hotspots are connected to the sources. Specific for the smaller scale is that a large seabed hotspot was identified in front of the most southern inlet of the Venice lagoon, which is in agreement with earlier observations.

For the Ave estuary, very limited observations were available at the start of the project. In order to estimate the maximum flow velocities and flow patterns relevant for the design and exact location within the estuary, measurements campaigns were carried out and a hydrodynamic model was set-up from scratch. Observations were carried out at selected locations within the estuary, having a length of about 2 km from a weir to the Atlantic Ocean. The aim of the observations and modelling was to understand the temporal and spatial variation of the flow velocity. The bathymetry was measured for the estuary and surrounding coastal waters. In absence of river discharge observations, a hydrological model was set-up for the Ave River basin,

resulting in a river discharge ranging from about 9 to 300 m³/s in the period June 2020 up to June 2022. We can conclude that the flow in the estuary is mainly determined by the tides and the river discharge, and the effect of wind on the flow is limited. During low river discharge, the observations and the hydrodynamic model show that the estuary is highly stratified, meaning that a fresh-brackish water layer is on top of oceanic water (salt wedge estuary). Simulated flow velocity magnitudes do not exceed 0.5 m/s in the area selected to implement the Bubble Barrier system during low river discharge. At mean and high river discharge, we have only limited observations. In November 2022 a maximum flow velocity magnitude was observed, being 0.63 m/s, in combination with a mixed and entirely fresh water column. Apparently, a higher river discharge occurred this day. Unfortunately, we did not have the meteorological data yet to estimate the river discharge from the hydrological model. From this observation we can conclude that a higher river discharge can result in flushing of the estuary. For the extreme river discharge of 300 m³/s and using the hydrodynamic model, we found that a maximal flow velocity magnitude in the water column can occur up to 1.9 m/s. Furthermore, we have highlighted a few areas with generally low dynamics during low river discharge, where marine litter may deposit or accumulate.

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1. Introduction to the MAELSTROM project

MAELSTROM is a project funded under the Topic CE-FNR-09-2020 Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter. MAELSTROM strives to provide answers and diversified solutions to the complex question to the removal and sustainable treatment of marine litter legacy. MAELSTROM contemplates the integration of complementary technologies for marine litter removal in different European coastal ecosystems, compounded with full-fledged circular economy and societal oriented solutions. In particular, the project (i) sets out a reliable multidisciplinary and scientifically sound approach for the assessment of marine debris distribution and impact on marine life in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas; (ii) designs and manufactures scalable, replicable and automated technologies, co-powered with renewable energy and second generation fuel, to identify, remove and sort marine litter; (iii) evaluates over time the performance of marine litter removal devices along with their impact on local ecosystems; (iv) integrates different technologies to track, sort and recycle all types of collected marine litter into valuable raw materials for future marketisation; (v) assesses the economic and societal impact of the MAELSTROM solutions providing also a comprehensive life-cycle assessment of the technologies and products; (vi) enhances social awareness about the marine litter issue and engages citizens and stakeholders in MAELSTROM activities; (vii) interplays with similar projects to maximize innovation uptake for marine litter removal within and outside the EU.

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2. MAELSTROM Consortium

The MAELSTROM project consortium consists of:

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3. Aims of the deliverable

3.1. Background

Two complementary scalable, replicable and automated technologies are applied and evaluated within MAELSTROM. The first technology is an automated cable-robot on a platform that removes litter from the sea bed, which is currently being applied in demo sites near Venice (Italy). The second technology is a Bubble Barrier that removes litter from rivers. This technology is being applied in the Ave estuary (Portugal). The collected litter is recycled and put back into the market. Besides reducing the amount of litter in the sea, MAELSTROM aims to raise awareness of the issue of plastic pollution.

In order to identify the locations where the technologies could possibly best be applied and to assess the impact of the litter removal on marine life, MAELSTROM makes use of numerical models. This Deliverable 2.2 describes the set-up of the different numerical models, their first results and their implications for each of the two demo sites. Out of the main project activities described in chapter 1, this deliverable contributes to (i) estimating marine debris distribution and (ii) giving details on the hydrodynamics that are used for the design technologies to remove marine litter. Furthermore, the field observations that were carried out in the Ave estuary in the framework of MAELSTROM are analysed. Since the aims for the two demo sites differ somewhat, we briefly describe the two demo sites first.

3.2. Demo sites

3.2.1. Venice coastal area (Italy)

The Venice Lagoon and its nearby coastal system (Gulf of Venice) are heavily impacted by anthropic pressures due to urbanisation, heavy marine traffic (commercial, tourism and fishing) and intense fish-farming activities. The lagoon is most often associated with tourism, recreational and commercial activities. However, in the coastal waters there is a strong influence of fishery and aquaculture activities. This affects the type of litter that is most commonly recovered in the area that needs to be simulated by the model. The sites for the cable robot first tests have been chosen in the Venice Lagoon and in the Gulf of Venice (MAELSTROM D5.1). So far, the cable robot was tested operationally in the inner shallow transitional waters and still needs to be tested in the open coastal waters. The results of the modelling activity aim to be of help to identify locations for possible further cleaning operations.

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The Adriatic Sea is a narrow elongated semi-enclosed basin having a shallow northern area (water depths of about 50 m), becoming deeper towards the south (Figure 3.1 left), reaching the largest depths (about 1200m) in the southern Adriatic pit. The northern seafloor is characterised by the presence of rocky agglomerates (*tegnue*) on the bottom, which act as traps for marine litter. Several of these agglomerates are located along the coastal area in front of the Venice lagoon. The Adriatic Sea is connected to the rest of the Mediterranean Sea through the Otranto Strait in the most southern part of the basin. A large number of freshwater sources (approximately a third of the total freshwater input in the Mediterranean) discharge in the Adriatic Sea, the largest of which is the Po River on the Italian coast.

The Venice Lagoon is located in the Northern Adriatic Sea, and it is the biggest lagoon in the Mediterranean Sea (area 550 km²). This lagoon is connected to the sea through three inlets and a network of channels which starts from each inlet, becoming narrower and shallower progressively going to the inner part of the lagoon. The bathymetry of the Venice lagoon is very complex, connecting very shallow areas (marshes < 0.5 m depth), moderate depth areas (around 1-1.5 m deep), deep channels from 2 to 7 m and ultradeep places (scour holes of up to 50 m deep). The lagoon receives a notable amount of freshwater from at least twelve rivers (natural and artificial) along the lagoon border and also from diffuse sources coming from the cities. The fresh water input into the coastal region will also transport litter into the coastal region. The amount of litter transported depends on the degree of urbanization in the river basin and the river discharge.

Sources of marine litter are connected to human activities. As so many activities take place in the area, there are many sources of marine litter. A recent survey (MAELSTROM D2.1) found that the main sources for seabed litter are public litter (domestic and touristic waste) and litter from shipping and from fishing.

Figure 3.1 Map of the Adriatic Sea, bathymetry used in the numerical model (left panel) and zoom in the northern area (right panel).

3.2.2. Ave estuary (Portugal)

Out of six possible locations in the Porto region, the Ave estuary was selected to implement the Bubble Barrier and solar panels for power generation (MAELSTROM D5.3). First field visits showed that the depth and width of the estuary was within the range in which existing Bubble Barriers have showed to be effective in collecting litter. For the location within the Ave estuary where the Bubble Barrier system was planned, the accessibility and the visibility are good, being in an urban area close to the tourist centre of Vila do Conde and the environmental monitoring center CMIA. The potential for a successful operation of the system, including the cooperation of local authorities, was found to be high. Furthermore, the impact of the marine litter removal by the Bubble Barrier system on the area and the marine ecosystem is expected to be high. The Bubble Barrier system can be installed close to the ocean. In the case it would be installed further upstream, litter from less potential sources would be removed. The maximal flow velocity in the estuary seemed to be sufficient low (about 0.5-0.7 m/s) to ensure a good performance of the system, causing that the litter is guided towards the estuarine bank by the Bubble Barrier (MAELSTROM D4.2). Still, the secondary aim to develop the system further for locations under the influence of tides is met. A drawback for the selection of the Ave estuary is that very limited observations on physical and environmental conditions and no hydrodynamic model were available, although it was assumed prior to starting MAELSTROM that all this would be readily available.

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The Ave river runs from a mountainous region (Serra da Cabreira) to its mouth in Vila do Conde (MAELSTROM D2.1). Vila do Conde has an area of 149.03 km² and (in 2019) 79 739 inhabitants¹. The Ave estuary is an urban estuary surrounded by the Vila do Conde municipality and is situated in the district of Porto (Figure 3.2 top). Near Vila do Conde, the Ave River flows over a weir into the Ave estuary which limits the extension of the estuary to a total length of about 2 km between the weir and the Atlantic Ocean (Figure 3.2 bottom). The estuary is mainly used for fishing and nautical-related activities. A recreational marina and shipyards are present along the estuary. The Bubble Barrier system is planned to be installed in a straight section near the estuary mouth (Figure 3.2 bottom). An ecological assessment was carried out in 2021 and 2022, showing that status of the Ave estuary can be classified as moderate to poor according to the assessment of nutrients and the biological element benthic macroinvertebrates (MAELSTROM, D2.3). In the field surveys considerable amounts of macrolitter (e.g. styrofoam, bags and plastic bottles) and microplastics (mostly in the size range 0.1-0.5 mm) were found. Sources of the litter seemed to be land-based, highlighting the potential impact of reducing the amount of litter transport to the sea by the Bubble Barrier system.

¹ <https://www.pordata.pt>

Figure 3.2 Map of the Ave River basin (top; Source: MAELSTROM D2.1, 2021) and the main features of the Ave estuary including the weir and the area where the Bubble Barrier system is planned (bottom).

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3.3. Objectives

The general aim of this activity is to adapt the new and already implemented hydrological and hydrodynamic models to represent hydrodynamic patterns of the Portuguese demo site and simulate macroplastic dispersal in Venice demo site. Numerical models of the Ave River mainly support the implementation of the Bubble Barrier system in terms of tides, water velocity and water column stratification. Numerical models of the Venice demo site aim to identify possible ML accumulation hotspots in sea floor, water column and beaches.

3.3.1. Venice coastal area

The geometry of the Venice lagoon and the Gulf of Venice is complex. The sources of marine litter are not well characterized, leading to a high uncertainty in the assessment of marine litter dispersion and accumulation. The aim of the numerical application is the identification of so-called “hotspots”, which are areas of large accumulation of marine litter. These hotspots have much higher concentrations of litter than most areas of the sea. Hotspots can be accumulation sites of beached or floating litter, and particularly marine litter on the seafloor. A hotspot on the seafloor can be due to local marine litter sources, which sink rapidly and accumulate on the seafloor over time, as well as due to specific current patterns transporting litter to a specific location, where it deposits. The modelling results obtained for this study indicate where the seafloor marine litter hotspots could be for future informed seafloor cleaning operations. Data on the presence of litter will provide an opportunity to assess the accuracy of the model predictions.

3.3.2. Ave estuary

Specific for the Ave estuary is that very limited physical and environmental observations were available. Hardly any flow velocity, depth level, water level or salinity recordings were available. For a successful functioning of the Bubble Barrier system, the flow velocity should not exceed the limit at which the Bubble Barrier has shown to be effective (about 0.5-0.7 m/s). For an estuary this means that the flow velocity should not be higher than this limit during a significant part of the tidal cycle. Therefore, a specific objective for the Portuguese demo site was to understand the flow dynamics in the estuary associated with river discharge and tides, in order to estimate the transport and fate of litter and to help the detailed design of the Bubble Barrier system.

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3.4. General approach

3.4.1. Venice coastal area

For the Venice coastal area existing hydrodynamic results have been used. These hydrodynamic results were combined with a particle tracking model to estimate locations where marine litter is likely to accumulate, using the marine litter sources described in MAELSTROM D2.1.

The water circulation for one year (2014) in the Venice lagoon and in the whole Adriatic Sea was calculated by the SHYFEM model (www.shyfem.org) applied under realistic meteo-marine forcing. The resulting flow velocities were used to calculate the dispersal of marine litter in the Venice and Adriatic area considering as sources the aquaculture farms, the main cities and the main rivers. Using the particle tracking model, the particles dispersal can be simulated considering the transport due to water current, the influence of the wind on superficial particles and the inertial effects, including also the particles sinking velocity. Hence, the particle tracking model was used to estimate the potential hotspots of marine litter accumulation on the seafloor. This result has been achieved considering each source typology, using the results of simulations over a period of 11 months.

3.4.2. Ave estuary

Since very limited observations and no flow velocity observations were available for the Ave estuary, we carried out the following activities:

- A bathymetric survey was carried out to obtain bed level in the entire estuary, needed for both the set-up of the hydrodynamic model and to prepare for the implementation of the Bubble Barrier system.
- Flow velocity and density variation were measured during a tidal cycle (about 13 hours) at selected locations (short-term), during the summer and the winter.
- For several weeks (long-term) flow velocity and density were monitored at two locations in the estuary.
- In absence of observations, a hydrological model was set-up to obtain river discharge.
- Finally, a hydrodynamic model was set-up to obtain flow velocity fields in the area of interest for different tidal and river discharge conditions.

The data collected in the long-term and short-term campaigns were used to calibrate the hydrodynamic model. Furthermore, the observations of flow and salinity variation

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were used to verify mixing of the fresh water from the river and the salty sea water. The results of the hydrodynamic model are characteristic (maximum) flow velocity maps during summer and winter river discharge, and during spring and neap tide. The results of the hydrodynamic model are beneficial for selecting the exact location and details of the design of the Bubble Barrier system (MAELSTROM 4.3). Using the hydrodynamic model, we can estimate the distribution of litter over the 2 km estuary due to the flow.

4. Venice coastal area

4.1. Background

The Adriatic Sea has a large extent (approximately a rectangle area of 200 x 800 km) and its bathymetry has complex features. The most relevant characteristics are a wide northern shelf area and a slope basin in the southern part. The Adriatic Sea has two deep pits in the middle (~ 250 m) and in the south (~ 1200 m) of the basin. The Adriatic water circulation is driven by the wind and tidal variations. The complexity of the interaction between meteo-marine conditions and geological-morphological characteristics makes this basin a challenge to model from the oceanographic point of view. The main general circulation is characterised by a cyclonic circulation along the coasts and two or three central gyres in the southern, and in the middle basin, that sometimes appear also in the northern part of the basin (Figure 4.1) (Cushman-Roisin et al. 2007, Umgiesser et al. 2022, Lipizer et al. 2010).

Figure 4.1 Schematic layout of Adriatic Sea currents. Red superficial current, blu bottom current. Figure credits: Tomobe 2003 - Own work based on Struje u Jadranu [Adriatic Sea currents] (in Croatian). University of Zagreb, Faculty of Science. Retrieved on 14 May 2012., CC BY-SA 3.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=19433350>

The Venice lagoon is located in the north-west part of the Adriatic Sea. In addition to a very complex bathymetry, its circulation is driven by wind and tidal variations. Intense events of wind and large tidal variation can occur, influencing the total water level inside the lagoon, with an impact on the transport of litter from the sea into the lagoon and vice versa. In general, the water circulation in the Venice lagoon has an extremely variable pattern with flood and ebb flows from the three inlets connecting the lagoon to the sea.

The northern Adriatic Sea and the Venice lagoon are characterised by intense human activity, both along the Italian and Croatian coasts. Several studies assessed the marine litter presence on the water column, seafloor and beaches in the Adriatic Sea and in the Gulf of Venice. A critical review is available in the deliverable MAELSTROM D2.1. Moreover, online resources are available to assess the distribution of marine litter in the Adriatic Sea and in the Gulf of Venice such as the EMODNET Chemistry data portal (<https://www.emodnet.eu/en/human-activities>) or the LITTERBASE portal (<https://litterbase.owi.de/litter>). They offer the possibility to access interactively the maps and reports on several typologies of litter in different locations (beach, water column, seafloor) covering all of the Adriatic Sea coastal areas. A litter inventory of the AQUA-LIT project is available to visualise the litter originated by aquaculture or fishing activities as a static map, considering several matrices in different sea areas. This inventory includes only the Italian coast in the Adriatic Sea. The general finding is that, overall, the areas that have the most seafloor marine litter extend over a long stripe along the Italian coast. They include the area in the Gulf of Trieste, the coastal areas in front of the Venice lagoon, and areas in front to the Po river down to the Gulf of Manfredonia. Along the Croatian coastline the areas with the highest concentration of marine litter appear to be distributed from Losjani to Zara and along the southern part of the Albanian coastal area. This information is biased by the field data survey available and thus only represents a first assessment, though useful to keep in mind when analysing our results.

For the Adriatic Sea the main sources of marine litter are large rivers, big coastal cities and intense tourism, intense commercial fisheries and mussel farming and heavy shipping traffic. The Adriatic Sea is a very highly polluted region in terms of beach litter with high presence of aquaculture related litter such as mussel nets (Strafella et al. 2019). The Po River is the most important river in terms of discharge in the northern Italian coast and it is estimated to discharge 120 tons/year of macrolitter (Van der Wal et al. 2015). The contribution of sea-based sources relative to land-based sources is high in the Adriatic Sea especially for the Italian coast and indicates the relevance of aquaculture activities as sources of marine litter represented overall by mussel nets.

The seafloor litter in the Adriatic Sea reaches one of the highest average densities worldwide (913 +/- 80 items/km, Pasquini et al. 2016). Plastic is dominant (80% of numbers, 62% of weight) and consists of bags, sheets and fishing nets. Higher quantities of litter were found in coastal areas close to the sources of rivers, cities and mussel farms. Plastic hotspots seem located in front of the Po River and tourist seaside cities

(Pasquini et al. 2016, Strafella et al. 2019). The most affected locations are the stations close to the coast within 30 m depth. The percentage and composition of the seafloor marine litter is reported also by Fortibuoni et al. (2019). Plastic represents the majority (86.3% numbers and 77% weight) of litter items. The main categories are short-term and single-use objects. The most abundant subcategories are sheets, industrial packaging, plastic sheeting 28.3%, bags 14%, food containers 9%, plastic bottles 8%, and mussel and oyster nets 6%.

Several numerical studies to simulate the marine litter dispersal in the Adriatic Sea have been presented (Liubaseteva et al. 2016, 2018). A concise review is available in the MAELSTROM deliverable (MAELSTROM D2.1). Following the literature, to successfully simulate the marine litter dispersal and accumulation, modelling needs to consider not only the hydrodynamic water transport, but also the Stokes effect and the inertial drift. The sinking behaviour of the marine litter is taken into account by applying a sinking velocity. In this study we are focusing on macrolitter having size greater than 0.5 mm.

4.2. Detailed approach

The applied numerical tool consists of a three-dimensional hydrodynamic model that reproduces the water current evolution in the domain of the case study area. While the focus of the project is the Venice lagoon and the Gulf of Venice, we developed our study to cover the whole Adriatic Sea, including the sources of marine litter coming from the whole of the Adriatic coastline.

The water current transport is simulated by the hydrodynamic model under realistic forcing conditions. The dispersal of marine litter is calculated using a particle tracking model developed to take into account the sinking velocity of the particles, as well as the effect of the bottom rocky sea floor on particle bottom transport.

Using this numerical approach, we performed simulations that model the dispersal of marine litter, from which we determined hotspots, where high concentrations of marine litter accumulate. The model results were used to screen for clean-up location, where the concentration of marine litter is high with respect to surrounding areas.

A crucial aspect of the model is the characterization of the main sources of marine litter in the Adriatic Sea and in the Gulf of Venice. The public litter represents the first source of beached marine litter followed by non-sourced litter, aquaculture and fishing (mussel nets). In case of macrolitter seabed composition, the main sources are public activity (domestic and touristic waste), followed by shipping activity and

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fisheries. The macrolitter composition of the seabed is derived from the field surveys in the Gulf of Venice and is very similar to the beached marine litter composition. The data indicates a high spatial heterogeneity of marine litter related to a high variability, both in temporal distribution and abundance of each marine litter type. The main categories of marine litter and an approximate percentage is reported in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Main categories of marine litter founded in beach and seafloor matrices, with approximative percentage and estimated material specification.

Category	%	Definition	Composition	Symbol	Density
C1	26	Fragments	Polyethylene/polypropylene	-	0.9
C2	24	Food derived	Polyethylene/polypropylene	-	0.9
C3	15	Cigarette buds	Celluloses	CA	1.28
C4	10	Fishery derived	Nylon 6	PA	1.05
C5	7	Polystyrene mix	Polystyrene	EPS	< 1.025
C6	5	Cotton	Textile	-	n.d.
C7	4	Bags	Polyethelyne, pvc	PVC	1.4
C8	9	Mixed	Mix	-	n.d.

Each source gives rise to different categories of macrolitter reported in Table 4.2 with their composition. It is evident that the most relevant difference in composition is between land-based sources of marine litter (rivers, cities and diffuse sources) and sea-based sources (aquaculture and fisheries). They can be grouped in these two macro-groups.

Table 4.2 Main sources identified from literature and their composition in terms of the marine litter categories.

Source	Categories						
Rivers	C1	C2	C3		C5	C6	
Cities	C1	C2	C3		C5	C6	
Diffuse sources	C1	C2	C3		C5	C6	
Aquaculture				C4			C7
Fisheries				C4			C7

Based on these considerations, we assume as main sources of marine litter in our model the rivers, the cities and the aquaculture plants.

4.3. Hydrodynamic model

The setup, calibration and validation of the SHYFEM hydrodynamic model were performed during the MarGnet project (D5.1). A short description of the application is here reported.

4.3.1. Geometry

The model represents the Adriatic Sea basin using a finite element grid (87016 nodes and 158180 elements) with the horizontal resolution varying from a few hundred meters along the coast to 10 kilometres in the middle of the basin. The domain includes the main lagoons (including the Venice lagoon) and the Po River system and it has an open boundary in the south along the Otranto Strait. The water column is discretized using 38 vertical z layers, having increasing layer thickness going from 1 m at the surface to 100 m at the bottom.

Figure 4.2 shows the numerical grid and the positions of the *tegnue* area (red areas) for the northern Adriatic, including the Venice lagoon and its coastal zone. The *tegnue* structures are offshore rocky areas covering the bottom of the northern coastal area of the Adriatic Sea and several field surveys found aquaculture marine litter trapped on such rocky seafloors.

Figure 4.2 Map of the outcrops areas (tegnue) in the North Adriatic Sea. Their location is registered with a specific element type (red elements) in the numerical grid used for the numerical simulations in aquaculture scenarios.

4.3.2. Set-up and calibration

The hydrodynamic model was applied using realistic forcing. Tidal oscillation was imposed as a water level time series at the open boundary, and it was extracted from the measured time series at the Otranto tide gauge. Wind and surface forcings are provided by the nonhydrostatic meteorological model MOLOCH developed by CNR-ISAC (Davolio et al. 2015, 2017; Stocchi and Davolio 2017). More details of the implementation are in Ferrarin et al. 2019 and in the Margnet deliverable D5.1.

The hydrodynamic model was run for one entire year, 2014, with the first month considered as a spin-up period. The model was validated by comparing model results with data obtained in field campaigns conducted in 2014, covering the portion of the North Adriatic coast from Ancona to Trieste. Both temperature and salinity profile data were compared with the corresponding modelled profiles and the model was able to reproduce the dynamics of these variables with an error ranging between -0.5 to 1 psu in salinity and 0.5 °C in temperature. The averaged bias along the water column was less than 1 psu in salinity and 0.25 °C in temperature, respectively. This means that on average the model is able to reproduce the salinity and temperature with a sufficient capability to perform the numerical experiments of this study.

The verification of the model capability to reproduce the trajectories of floating particles was obtained by the comparison with the drifter trajectories modelled during an experiment in another year. In the experiment a pool of particles was used to represent all the possible trajectories of the real drifter. The comparison between the average trajectory calculated on all the virtual particles and the measured trajectory of the drifter shows the capability of the model to reproduce the drifter dispersal pattern. More details can be found in Umgiesser et al. (2022).

4.4. Particle tracking modelling

4.4.1. Model formulation

The particle tracking model tracks Lagrangian particles in 3D and is run offline, using the SHYFEM hydrodynamic outputs to evolve the particles. The equations for the Lagrangian module are:

$$X_{new} = X_{old} + \Delta t(u_a + u_d), Y_{new} = Y_{old} + \Delta t(v_a + v_d), Z_{new} = Z_{old} + \Delta t(w_a + w_d - w_s),$$

where X , Y and Z are the position coordinates of the particle, with u , v and w being the velocity components in those directions respectively. The subscripts *old* and *new* represent the old and new positions after a single time step Δt (taken as 5 minutes for

all our simulations). The subscripts a and d indicate the advective and diffusive velocity components respectively, while w_s is the settling velocity. The advection of the particles is carried out in each grid prism (i.e. the triangular element extended over the vertical layer) by computing the time needed for a particle to reach the border of the prism (either in the horizontal or vertical). If this time is larger than the time step, then the particle stays in the original prism, otherwise the particle leaves the element, either horizontally into a new element, or vertically into a new layer. There the advection is continued with the remaining time that is left from the old time step. The particle path in the prism is determined and the particle is advected along this path in a mass conserving way. The diffusion is carried out through a random walk model. A random walk velocity is chosen from the distribution with between u_d , where u_d is given by

$$u_d = \sqrt{(6A/\Delta t)}$$

and the velocity obtained with this formula is used in the formulas above for u_d , v_d and w_d , and where A is the turbulent diffusivity of the hydrodynamic model and Δt is the time step (Visser et al. 1997, Ghezzi et al. 2015). During the simulation the particles can interact with the domain boundaries in different ways, depending on the type of boundaries. The model has the possibility to stop all particles which come into contact with the coastline, simulating the beaching process. When a particle exits from the open boundary at the Otranto strait the particle is eliminated from the computational domain. The wind has an effect on the superficial particles changing their position due to the Stokes effect. This is parametrised in the model as function of the wind velocity and a Stokes parameter. The effect is calculated without to specify the submerged fraction of the particles. The inertial drift is defined to consider the inertia of the objects and is calculated as multiplicative factor on the advective transport.

The model allows for marine litter sinking, but once the bottom is reached the particle either stops at the bottom or can continue to be advected depending on the bottom characteristics. The model recognizes the position of the rocky structure (tegnue) and particles are stopped when they arrive on the bottom at these positions. The grid elements where particles are blocked at the bottom are specified based on what is known about the type of seabed characteristics in that location.

4.4.2. Simulations set-up and design

Each simulation uses the three-dimensional current field calculated by the hydrodynamic model as input for the particle tracking module.

The litter is represented as particles subjected on the surface to the Stokes drift effect due to the wind, which is prescribed as a matrix variable in space and in time during the simulation coherently with the forcing of the hydrodynamic field.

The sinking velocity of the particles is prescribed as a constant from measured data during the EASME/EMFF/2017/1.2.1.12/S2/05/SI2.789314 MarGnet project (deliverable D5.1). The final choice of the sinking velocity was determined after performing several test simulations with different values of sinking velocity. The particles with the highest sinking values reach the seafloor in a very short time (few hours to reach 50 m depth), meaning that in this case the effect of hydrodynamics is negligible as the seafloor distribution depends mainly on the position of the identified sources. On the other hand, a very low sinking velocity produces a behaviour more similar to microlitter and implies a very long permanence of the particles in the water column. Based on these tests we selected a sinking velocity of 0.0001 m/s, which ensures that the particles take on average around 1 week to reach the bottom in a water column of 50 m depth.

The sources of the marine litter used in the simulation are divided into three groups and simulated as:

1. Aquaculture: Particles released from predefined areas in the Northern Adriatic Sea where intense aquaculture activities are located.
2. Rivers: The contribution of marine litter from 80 rivers in the Adriatic are modelled. The number of particles released at each river is proportional to the river discharge, varying in time following the river discharge level.
3. Cities: marine litter from coastal cities with the number of particles proportional to the cities population.

Each different typology of source corresponds to a different simulation having a specific design of the numerical experiment.

Aquaculture design

The aquaculture sources are mostly representative of mussel farms. These activities release mainly mussel nets (rarely empty having always residual pieces of mussels

inside) and are located for the most part along the Italian coast and only in some points of the Croatian coast (see Figure 4.3).

In the model they are represented as seeding areas having different surfaces. The simulation is designed to release the particles on the surface layer every day for the 11 months long simulation. The number of particles released in each area is calculated to maintain the density of particles released in each area constant.

In the aquaculture simulation the trapping effect of the rocky seabed located in the northern area of the Adriatic Sea is activated (see Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.3: distribution of aquaculture plants in the North Adriatic Sea estimated by EMODNET data (www.emodnet.eu) and integrated with expert knowledge.

Rivers design

The rivers are recognized as an important source of marine litter and recent studies (Gonzales-Fernandez al. 2018, Meijer et al., 2021) demonstrated that not only do big rivers contribute to the marine litter budget, but also small rivers can contribute significantly. In this simulation 80 rivers are included (Figure 4.4) covering all the basin coastline. The particles are released hourly from each river and are proportional to

the water discharge value. The number of released particles from each river is proportional to the river water discharge and it is variable in time if the timeseries of water discharge is available, otherwise it is set as constant. This means that in periods of high river discharge, there is a higher number of marine litter particles released.

During periods of high river discharge, the simulation can produce a huge number of particles in a short space of time, making long time simulations very difficult to perform. In order to limit the number of particles in the simulation and at the same time maintain an accurate representation of all the river inputs (from the smallest to the largest), the entire study period was divided into separate monthly runs of the particle tracking model.

Figure 4.4 position of the rivers in the Adriatic basin adopted as marine litter sources.

Cities design

The cities can produce marine litter because of mismanagement of waste (MAELSTROM D2.1). We considered 53 cities as marine litter sources selected based on having a population of more than 50 000 inhabitants (Figure 4.5).

To evaluate the marine litter released by each city we used estimates based on the literature (Amadei et al. 2022), where it is determined that the marine litter produced

by 1 inhabitant in 1 year in Europe is 114 kg/person. Considering that on average 22% of waste is mismanaged (Kaandorp et al. 2020), this implies an average yearly input of marine litter of 25.08 kg/pers.

The number of inhabitants of each city was calculated adding the number of residents and the tourist visitors. This value is multiplied by the factor representing the marine litter per person per second to give the intensity of particles released by each city for the simulation.

In this case, the number of particles released is constant in time and the simulation was divided into monthly runs.

Figure 4.5 Position of the cities in the Adriatic basin adopted as marine litter sources.

4.5. Analysis methodology

We defined the following descriptors for all the simulations:

- total number of released particles
- % of particles on the bottom layer
- % of particles beached

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- density of particles calculated on a regular grid (0.005° resolution) on the bottom layer
- density of particles calculated on a regular grid (0.005° resolution) in the water column

These descriptors are calculated at the end of each month in all the simulations (aquaculture, rivers and cities).

For each month, the map of particle density in the surface and bottom layers are produced, showing both the whole basin and a zoom on the Northern Adriatic area. In addition, maps of the seasonally averaged horizontal currents were produced, to assess the main pattern of transport driving the marine litter distribution.

4.6. Results

The distribution of the marine litter in the Adriatic Sea was assessed by performing the numerical simulations, considering both the land based marine litter sources (rivers and cities), as well as marine sources (aquaculture). In Figure 4.6 we show maps of the depth averaged seasonal currents (speed and direction) as a summary of the circulation driving the transport of marine litter in the Adriatic. One of the main currents for the Adriatic circulation is the West Adriatic Current (WAC) along the Italian coast, which seems to be a main transport pathway flowing from north to south. This current is present throughout the year, though is strongest in the winter period (bottom right panel) when overall there are stronger currents in the whole basin. In the south there is a strong persistent gyre located over the Southern Pit, the deepest part of the Adriatic. The circulation in the North Adriatic is generally weaker than the rest of the basin, particularly in the more offshore parts, and nearer to the Croatian coastline. Overall, the general circulation pattern is as has been observed in previous work (Figure 4.6, see Umgiesser et al. 2022 and references therein).

Figure 4.6 Maps of Adriatic current speed and direction vertically averaged for seasonal averaged values: Spring (top left, February-March-April), Summer (top right, May-June-July), Autumn (bottom left, August-September-November) and Winter (bottom right, November-December).

4.6.1. Hotspots for sinking marine litter in aquaculture

Maps of the density of particles on the seafloor are shown in Figure 4.7 to Figure 4.10, showing snapshots at the end of each month, both for the whole Adriatic basin and a closeup on the Northern Adriatic. They reveal that the area in front of the Po River and the area of the Gulf of Venice have the largest accumulation of marine litter over the entire period. The spread of the marine litter from the north towards the south demonstrates the effect of the along coast transport on the particle distribution due to the West Adriatic Current seen in Figure 4.6. In the early months the highest concentration of litter is confined to the Italian coastline in the northern part of the basin. Eventually, though, more particles are transported along the Italian coast

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down to the Southern Adriatic. At the central Adriatic, particles from the coast begin to be transported offshore along the depth isolines. Further to the south, the presence of the strong southern gyre initially acts as a barrier, restricting the particles to its periphery. Though as the gyre evolves and contracts in size in the second half of the year, marine litter starts to be entrained within, arriving at the bottom of the deep pit, the deepest part of the Adriatic Sea. Over the entire period, while there is a big change in the distribution of the particles on the whole basin scale, the pattern in the Northern Adriatic remains fairly stable, with most of the litter concentrated near the western coast, along the Po basin and the Venice coastal area.

Figure 4.7 Maps of seafloor particle density for the months of February to April going from the top row to the bottom, for the aquaculture source simulation. The density values shown are for the 28th of each month, both for the entire Adriatic basin (left column) and a closeup of the Northern Adriatic (right column).

Figure 4.8 Maps of seafloor particle density for the months of May to July going from the top row to the bottom, for the aquaculture source simulation. The density values shown are for the 28th of each month, both for the entire Adriatic basin (left column) and a closeup of the Northern Adriatic (right column).

Figure 4.9 Maps of seafloor particle density for the months of August to October going from the top row to the bottom, for the aquaculture source simulation. The density values shown are for the 28th of each month, both for the entire Adriatic basin (left column) and a closeup of the Northern Adriatic (right column).

Figure 4.10 Maps of seafloor particle density for the months of November to December going from the top row to the bottom, for the aquaculture source simulation. The density values shown are for the 28th of each month, both for the entire Adriatic basin (left column) and a closeup of the Northern Adriatic (right column).

Table 4.3 indicates the total accumulated number of released particles calculated every month, along with the accumulated number and percentage of beached and seafloor particles.

Table 4.3 Total number of released, beached and on the seabed for each month

Aquaculture						
id	month	total	beached	%	seafloor	%
2	February	29029	1207	4	23190	80
3	March	60060	3399	6	49046	82
4	April	90090	4709	5	71684	80
5	May	121121	6711	6	97318	80
6	June	151151	7920	5	119142	79
7	July	182182	9133	5	148595	82
8	August	213213	10142	5	175833	82
9	September	243243	11639	5	202683	83
10	October	274274	13752	5	221958	81
11	November	304304	16461	5	243747	80
12	December	332332	18779	6	277866	80

The total number of particles on the seafloor is almost always above 80%, while the number of beached particles is limited to 6% or below throughout. This limited beaching is because the aquaculture sources are not strictly close to the coast, making it possible for these particles to be advected away by the basin currents, avoiding beaching, before finally arriving on the seafloor.

In Figure 4.11 the particles in the water column are compared to the corresponding particles on the seafloor, as calculated at the end of each month indicated. The distribution of the particles in the water column reflects mostly the location of the areas of the aquaculture as defined in the model, where the particles are released. Only in December when the currents are strongest is there greater spatial distribution of particles in the water column. Thus, by the end of the month the highest concentration of marine litter is located on the seafloor away from the release zone, though almost totally confined to the western coastline, leaving the eastern part of the basin almost completely unaffected by the aquaculture marine litter sources.

Figure 4.11: Maps of density in the water column (top row) and at the seafloor (bottom row) for the aquaculture source simulation at the end of the months indicated.

4.6.2. Hotspots for sinking marine litter in rivers

In Figure 4.12 to Figure 4.15, we show monthly maps of seafloor litter for the simulations with the river as sources of marine litter. These sources reflect the land originated marine litter along the entire coastline, resulting in a more widely distributed pattern with respect to the aquaculture case, as now there are sources in the South Adriatic Sea (the Albania coast) and along its Eastern coastline (the coast of Croatia). As in the aquaculture case, the Western Adriatic Current is the strongest driver in transporting marine litter from the North to the Central and Southern Adriatic Sea.

While the area around the Po river has the highest density of litter throughout, there is a strong monthly variability in this concentration, due to the meteorological variation and the variation in river discharge. As to be expected, the highest density concentrations coincide with the months of highest discharge (February, November, December), with the summer months (June, July, August) characterized by low river discharge having the lowest concentrations.

High concentrations also occur in the eastern part of the southern Adriatic due to the high discharge of the Albanian rivers (Bojana, Mat, Ishm, Erzen, Shkumbi, Seman, Vijuse; numbers from 55 to 59 in Figure 4.4).

Figure 4.12 Maps of seafloor particle density for the months of February to April going from the top row to the bottom, for the river source simulation. The density values shown are for the 28th of each month, both for the entire Adriatic basin (left column) and a closeup of the Northern Adriatic (right column).

Figure 4.13 As in Figure 4.12, but now for the months of May to July going from the top row to bottom.

Figure 4.14 As in Figure 4.12, but now for the months of August to October going from the top row to the bottom.

Figure 4.15 As in Figure 4.12, but now for the months of November (top row) and December (bottom row).

In comparison with the aquaculture simulation, the pattern of particles reaching the deeper areas in the middle of the Adriatic Sea is less evident, with most of the particles confined to the coastal zone. This is to be expected given that the river source simulations are only monthly runs, as compared to the aquaculture simulation run over the entire 11 month period. However, in the North Adriatic there is a much higher concentration of marine litter than seen in the aquaculture simulations.

Table 4.4 reports the total number of accumulated particles released by all the rivers during the monthly simulation, along with the accumulated number and percentage of beached and seafloor particles. The variation in the total number is due to the variation in the river discharge. It indicates that around 30% or 37% of the particles

at the end of the month are on the bottom inside the domain. This value keeps more or less constant after the first two months, with a variation of 2%.

Table 4.4 Total number of released, beached and on the seabed for each month

Rivers						
id	month	total	beached	%	seafloor	%
2	February	563419	313279	56	169880	30
3	March	1059867	571763	54	338850	32
4	April	1486381	758982	51	522622	35
5	May	1936587	977594	50	713576	37
6	June	2248335	1137684	51	840180	37
7	July	2543306	1308699	51	942576	37
8	August	2851803	1492566	52	1047779	36
9	September	3086597	1630670	53	1124191	36
10	October	3355049	1781270	53	1209029	36
11	November	3918794	2109871	54	1399112	35
12	December	4754311	2562038	54	1669785	35

The percentage of beached particles generally ranges from about 50% to 56%. As the release of particles from rivers are at the coast there is a much higher level of beaching here than occurs in the aquaculture simulation.

In Figure 4.16 we compare the marine litter density in the water column with the seafloor values. The behaviour of the particles in the water column is more variable than the bottom particles, as the transport by current is stronger. Most of the litter in the water column is near the coastline, while the bottom litter is more widely distributed. This suggests that the pattern visible on the bottom is produced first from a surface transport and - successively - by the transport along the bottom, following the bathymetric gradient. As in the case of the aquaculture sources, there is very little marine litter in the central basin and on the eastern coastline, suggesting that even with more distributed sources there is no dynamical pathway to bring litter to these eastern areas on the Croatian coastline.

Figure 4.16 Maps of density in the water column (top row) and at the seafloor (bottom row) for the river source simulations at the end of the months indicated.

4.6.3. Hotspots for sinking marine litter in cities

The results of the simulations having city sources are shown in Figure 4.17 to Figure 4.20. The maps indicate that the wide distribution of the city sources leads to the largest dispersal of particles in the whole basin, with respect to the other source types. Despite the fact that the rate of input of the city marine litter is constant, there is a strong monthly variability in the density distribution, both in the entire basin and in the northern region. This strong variability overall may reflect the hydrodynamic variability, as the wide distribution of these sources provides a constant supply of markers of the near shore currents around the entire basin. It is possible to find particles on the sea bottom close to the coast, but also in the middle of the shallow part of the Northern Adriatic Sea and along the border of the deeper holes (Figure 3.1, bathymetry of the Adriatic Sea).

Figure 4.17 Maps of seafloor particle density for the months of February to April going from the top row to the bottom, for the city source simulation. The density values shown are for the 28th of each month, both for the entire Adriatic basin (left column) and a closeup of the Northern Adriatic (right column).

Figure 4.18 As in Figure 4.17, but now for the months of May to July going from the top row to the bottom.

Figure 4.19 As in Figure 4.17, but now for the months of August to October going from the top row to the bottom.

Figure 4.20 As in Figure 17 but now for the months of November (top row) and December (bottom row).

Table 4.5 reports the total accumulated number of particles released in the simulations every month and the percentage of particles beached and on the bottom. Every month an almost constant percentage (around 25 %) of particles arrive on the bottom, while the percentage of beached particles remain fixed at 44 %.

Table 4.5 Total number of released, beached and on the seabed for each month

Cities						
id	month	total	beached	%	seafloor	%
2	February	531758	233186	44	135171	25
3	March	1122354	492566	44	276750	25
4	April	1693361	746505	44	413039	24
5	May	2283957	1006617	44	560381	25
6	June	2854964	1247541	44	705011	25
7	July	3445560	1505295	44	854619	25
8	August	4036156	1762430	44	1008047	25
9	September	4607163	2017078	44	1130275	25
10	October	5197759	2274729	44	1270929	24
11	November	5768766	2542187	44	1399826	24
12	December	6359362	2800785	44	1519749	24

The high beaching percentage, though less than the river cases, reflect the fact that, like rivers, the city sources are distributed along the coast. However, as the rate of release of particles is constant at each city, only varying from city to city, the percentage of beaching remains stable at 44 %.

Figure 4.21 shows the density of particles averaged at the end of the month in the water column (top row) and the corresponding density on the seafloor (bottom row). The fraction of the particles still travelling in the water column is limited to the coastal areas closest to the sources of marine litter. From these maps we see that the city sources produce higher marine litter concentration on the eastern coastline than was seen in the aquaculture and river simulations. It seems that marine litter along the eastern coast depends on local litter sources, and not subject to sources on the western coast, where there is no dynamic pathway for litter to go from west to the east.

Figure 4.21 Maps of density in the water column (top row) and at the seafloor (bottom row) for the city source simulations at the end of the months indicated.

4.6.4. Combination of potential seafloor hotspots

In order to identify the potential hotspots of marine litter in the Venice Lagoon and its coastal region and to summarise the results for future investigations, the time averaged distribution of bottom marine litter was calculated over the entire time period (from February to December) for each of the source types. For each source type a weight is assigned based on the work of Kaandorp et al. (2020): for the Mediterranean, plastic marine litter accounted approximately for 61% from cities, 32% from rivers, and 6% due to aquaculture and fisheries. Figure 4.22 shows the averaged marine litter density, keeping values above the threshold of 75 particles/m² in order to isolate potential hotspots. This approach allowed the identification of accumulation areas having high marine litter values that persist throughout the entire year. These locations can be characterised as potential hotspots which need to be investigated in the future by ground truthing measurements in order to assess the robustness of the approach and of the model performance.

The distribution over the entire Adriatic (Figure 4.22 left) shows that hotspots are connected to the sources, with the cities source simulations producing the greatest number of hotspots, followed by rivers. Not surprisingly, the largest river hotspot occurs near the Po River, though some notable areas can be seen in the central Croatian coast and in the South along the Albanian coast. The aquaculture hotspots are mostly confined to the Northern Adriatic, near the Venice coastal area, except for two hotspots in the Central Adriatic region. Focusing on the Venice coastal area

(Figure 4.22 right), one large seabed hotspot was identified from the aquaculture simulation in front of the most southern inlet of the Venice lagoon, though overlapping with smaller hotspots due to the river sources. Overall, the river source simulations produce more hotspots, a higher number of which are further offshore. Finally, from the simulation with city sources we identified some small potential hotspots in the sea, while larger hotspots occurred in the Venice lagoon.

Figure 4.22 Maps indicating hotspots for the different sources, aquaculture (red), rivers (blue) and cities (green). The density values are averaged over the entire period (February to December) and then weighted on the basis of the relevance of the source typology reported in Kaandorp et al. 2020.

4.7. Discussion

4.7.1. Comparison with observations

Our results on the distribution of seafloor marine litter in the Adriatic Sea is qualitatively consistent with published data. The coastal areas are intensely affected by marine litter pollution in the water ranging from 0 to 30 m (MAELSTROM deliverable D2.1). Figure 4.23 shows an inventory by AQUA-LIT on the presence of marine litter on the sea floor originating from aquaculture and/or fisheries, and the plastic abundance on the seafloor presented in Pasquini et al. (2016). Furthermore, observations at 32 stations on the seafloor are available from MAELSTROM 2.1 (Figure 4.24). A qualitative comparison of the model results and these earlier studies indicates that the model can correctly reproduce the pattern of seabed marine litter along the Italian coast and is also qualitatively in agreement with the available data along the Croatian and Albanian coast. We can conclude that the main patterns of seabed marine litter are identified with an acceptable agreement. Still, for a quantitative verification in-situ observations are needed.

Figure 4.23 Percentage of litter on the seabed originating from aquaculture (only the squares; left panel; Source AQUALIT Project); Distribution of seafloor plastic litter (right panel; source: Pasquini et al., 2016).

Figure 4.24 Total amount of marine litter (ML) items monitored on the seafloor at 32 stations (MAELSTROM D2.1).

Focusing on the demo site area in the Adriatic Sea, the seabed data analysis of the EMODNET data in the MAELSTROM D2.1 indicated as most impacted the areas close

to the coast and the area directly south of the Venice lagoon (south of the Chioggia inlet). The city of Chioggia in the southern part of the Venice Lagoon, hosts the most important fishing fleet in the Adriatic Sea. The area around this inlet is strongly impacted by fishing activities and the model identified potential hotspots in this area due to aquaculture and rivers sources. The field data indicates that the Po delta is affected by the inputs from the river. The Po is the largest river in the basin with a length of 673 km and a drainage basin of 71,000 km². It flows through one of the most productive agricultural and industrial areas, entering the northern Adriatic Sea through a large delta with five distributaries. The model simulation correctly identifies the hotspots in the river simulation (Figure 4.12 to Figure 4.15). In the final potential hotspots map (Figure 4.22) the contribution of the aquaculture litter seems most relevant in creating the potential hotspots in the Po area.

For what concerns the hotspots in the Venice lagoon, the model indicates that the sea bottom hotspots are in the areas close to the main cities, such as Venice, Mestre, Chioggia and Lido. Since the depth of the lagoon is very shallow and the set-up of simulation imposes a sinking velocity, this result is strongly correlated with the accuracy of the input sources. Unfortunately, there is only limited data of marine litter in the lagoon and surrounding areas, making an estimation of the main sources challenging.

4.7.2. Confidence in hotspots

The resulting maps of potential hotspots (Figure 4.22 and underlying maps) offer a framework for both numerical and experimental works. The pattern recognized as main dispersal trajectories of marine litter are useful to provide evidence of areas with higher potential risk of seabed marine pollution. The open question is how much confidence we can have in these results. The reliability of the maps crucially depends on the assumptions underpinning the study, namely the implementation of the main physical processes and the accuracy of the inputs of marine litter.

The hydrodynamic and particle tracking model were verified, so it is possible to have a high confidence in the hydrodynamic field and the transport pattern. The marine litter dispersal is implemented by considering fixed sinking velocities, and not density driven buoyancy. A low sinking velocity is used within the range of measured ones, to justify the application of a dispersal model. The use of higher sinking velocities means the period of horizontal transport is relatively short and the particles do not travel in the water column far from the release points. The shape and volume of the objects are neglected, since their effect on the sinking velocity is hardly known for macrolitter.

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This justifies the approach to use only one constant sinking velocity, but also puts limits on the range of categories of objects that is represented in this study.

The interactions of the macrolitter with the seafloor is another open question. We assumed that in the rocky bed marine litter deriving from aquaculture (net, stripes, ropes) is trapped and thus is stopped in the model. In fact, the interaction with the seabed should take into account the bottom roughness with a velocity threshold needed in order to resuspend an object, but more study is needed in order to understand this process.

Finally, the uncertainty in estimation of the input of marine litter from different sources is large and represents the greatest weakness on the accuracy of the results. Each source is characterised by intensity and its temporal variability and spatial extension of the release area. In the case of rivers and aquaculture the intensity can be approximated, and the temporal variability can be estimated by the river discharge or considering the timing of the activity. The spatial extension of these sources can be defined by the natural limits of the sources. In the case of cities, the temporal variation could be included considering the temporal variation in the population fluxes, if available. Instead, the spatial extensions of the sources are roughly approximated, using distributed points or parts of the coastlines. From experiences gathered during cleaning operations within MAELSTROM, it is known that the point where the waste is managed can act as a litter source, though it is not the only unique point of litter release.

5. Ave estuary

5.1. Background

5.1.1. Geometry

The Ave estuary connects the Ave river with the Atlantic Ocean in an urban environment surrounded by Vila Do Conde (Figure 3.2). It is a small estuary where the salt water can intrude over a length of about 2 km, until a weir that is associated with an historical watermill constructed in the 16th century. Therefore, the estuary can be considered as the water body from the weir to the Atlantic Ocean. The Ave estuary presents a NE-SW orientation. Its shore-to-shore distance is about 100 metres, being within the range of 80 and 200 m. Due to the small size, and also to the configuration of its margins with respect to predominant wind directions, we expect that the effect of wind on the water circulation is limited. The estuary is protected from oceanic storms by two breakwaters: the northern breakwater, which is about 350 m long, and the southern jetty, which is about 270 m long (Dias et al., 2011; APA, 2014). Hence, effects of the waves are expected to be limited inside the estuary.

The Ave estuary is a very shallow estuary with bed levels generally around 4 m below Mean Sea Level (MSL; Figure 5.1). Old bathymetric data were available, but these were too outdated to be considered. A bathymetric campaign was carried out within the scope of the MAELSTROM project, following Bio et al. (2022). This method enabled to reference the observed bed level height to the MSL, which was a challenge since no observations from a water level station were available in the Ave estuary. The bathymetric campaign was performed such that it covers not only the area selected to implement the Bubble Barrier system, but also the rest of the estuary such that it can be used as the basis for the hydrodynamic model. The sampling area included the entire estuarine region as well as the surrounding coastal area (right panel of Figure 5.1), revealing that maximal water depth occurs near the weir, being maximally about 8 m.

Medium and small vessels navigate in the estuary. Due to the generally low water depth, sedimentation is a risk for navigation. The estuary needs to be dredged regularly to maintain its water depth for navigation. Due to the configuration of the estuary including bends, the depth is highest in the outer bend, being in the north-west of the estuary. This is the urban margin, which is delimited by a rock wall. On the opposite side of the channel (inner bend) the bed level changes more gradually and sedimentation tends to occur. In this inner bend more vegetated areas can be

found, except for the shipyard region (Figure 3.1 bottom), where a small breakwater was constructed to protect the structures from erosion. In this area the width of the estuary was artificially reduced for navigation purposes.

Figure 5.1 Bathymetry of the surrounding coastal area (left) and the Ave estuary measured in July 2021 within the scope of MAELSTROM (right). The bed level is with respect to the MSL. The length of the Ave estuary from the weir (upper right) to the breakwater in the lower left is 2 km.

5.1.2. Main hydrodynamic forcing

The tides are mainly semidiurnal, having a period of 12.4 hours (Iglesias et al., 2021). The river discharge into the estuary at the weir averages $40 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ (Rocha et al., 2019). An analysis of the historical data between 1978 and 2000 available from Sistema Nacional de Informação de Recursos Hídricos (SNIRH²) revealed a seasonal pattern, with higher discharge in the winter months (November to March) and lower river discharge during summer months (June to October) (Figure 5.2), coinciding with the

² <https://snirh.apambiente.pt/>

precipitation patterns in the region (Gomez-Gesteira et al., 2011). Furthermore, extreme river discharge events were also recorded, with values of 450, 360 and 390 m³/s, which were recorded in April of 1979, January 1982 and March of 1990, respectively. The discharge is directly related to rainfall, as no (hydropower) dams are located near the Ave estuary. The two main dams in the Ave river are the Ermal and the Andorinhas dams, which are located at a distance of more than 50 km from the coast. Considering the bends of the river, the distance is higher when following the path along the river. However, some water is likely to be collected associated with industrial and agricultural activities. Please note that the data presented in Figure 5.2 is outdated. Changes during the last 20 years in the margins or in the main course of the flow (due to dams, artificial canals), in different industrial/agricultural activities and in climate may have resulted different rainfall patterns and a different temporal variation in river discharge.

Figure 5.2 Monthly mean river discharge at the estuarine region (black line). The upper and lower dashes represent the maximum and minimum river discharge values measured for each month during the sampling period (1978-2000).

5.1.3. Impact of litter

The Ave estuary is a highly urbanized region, where many river activities (e.g. canoeing) take place. Several potential sources of debris were identified along the river and estuary, such as port facilities, fishing activities, wastewater treatment plants, marinas, tributaries, intensive agricultural areas, livestock farms, and industries (APA, 2014; Rocha et al., 2013; Padilha, 2022; MAELSTROM D2.1). All these activities are potential sources of floating marine litter. There are very few studies performed in the Ave estuary regarding the abundance of marine litter. González-Fernández et al. (2021) performed an observational campaign in the Ave and reported

a mean floating litter flux of 9.97 items/h, which can produce an annual floating macrolitter flow of approximately 87306 items. Padilha (2022) performed seasonal campaigns along a year. The annual floating macrolitter flux value in the Ave estuary was approximately 7.4 items/h, but there is a strong variability among seasons, with values of 3.8 items/h in summer and in autumn, 13.9 items/h in winter and 5.6 items/h in spring. This is in line with the finding in MAELSTROM D2.3, that reported 16-19 items/hour from visual counting from a boat.

Padilha (2022) also analysed the materials and sources of the debris. The most common material was plastic, and the most recorded item styrofoam pieces, followed by plastic bottles, indicating that the sources of this litter are probably public litter, tourism and fishing activities. This also explains the abundance of cigarette butts and filters. All this litter is expected to have a substantial impact on the ocean and adjacent coastal regions, which also includes an important ornithological natural reserve (Ribeiro et al., 2016).

5.2. Approach and reading guide

Facing the limited field data and absence of available models, we carried out field campaigns, set-up a hydrological model for the Ave river basin and set-up a hydrodynamic model for the estuarine region. The field studies included a bathymetric survey, short-term (12.5 hours) and long-term (several weeks) campaigns. Figure 5.3 shows the locations and

Table 5.1 summarizes the period and conditions of the campaigns. For various reasons, the timing of observations was not according to plan. Since the intended CTD's were not available in time, it was not possible to carry out the short-term campaigns within the periods of the long-term campaigns, as planned. River discharge is no longer measured since 2000. Therefore, we set-up a hydrological model to estimate discharge. The meteorological data used to force this hydrological model becomes available with a delay up to 9 months, explaining why no discharge time series is yet available for the latest long-term campaigns (see section 5.5).

Aiming to understand the temporal and spatial variation of the flow velocity in the estuary, and particularly in the area where the Bubble Barrier system is planned to be implemented (Figure 3.2), we have analysed observations from a boat sailing across the estuary (short-term, section 5.3), we have analysed observations at selected locations (long-term, section 5.4) and we have set-up a 3-dimensional (3D) hydrodynamic model to give insight in the flow velocity distribution (section 5.6). Only during the short-term campaigns the river discharge is known, which was relatively low during these campaigns. Since the river discharge is an important condition for the hydrodynamic model, we have only obtained maximal flow velocity maps for low river discharge. For higher river discharge we show a maximal flow velocity observed during a long-term campaign and we estimate maximal flow velocity based on an extreme river discharge (section 5.7).

Figure 5.3 Location of the sampling points in the Ave estuary for the short-term and the long-term campaigns (first at location 1, and at location 1* the second campaign).

Table 5.1 Overview of the field observations that were carried out within the framework of MAELSTROM

Measurement	Where	What	When	Simulated river discharge (m ³ /s)	Remarks
Bathymetric sounding	Estuary and mouth	Sounding	September 2021	-	
Short-term "Summer"	CMIA-Sicnave	ADCP and multiparametric probe casts	19 October 2021 8:50-19:50	9	
Short-term Winter	CMIA-Sicnave	ADCP and multiparametric probe casts	17 January 2022 8:50-19:43	18	
Long-term 1	Locations 1 and 2	Near bed: ADCP+CTD Near surface: CTD	28 June-13 July 2022	10 (in first 4 days); later unknown	The ADCP and near-bed CTD were covered in mud
Long-term 2	Locations 1* and 2	Near bed: ADCP+CTD Near surface: CTD	31 October -15 December 2022	Unknown	Successful, except that something hit the ADCP and data is not reliable after 22 November

5.3. Short-term campaigns

5.3.1. Methodology

Both the short-term and long-term campaigns were performed during summer and winter conditions, meaning respectively a low and high river discharge (Figure 5.2). The short-term campaigns were carried out from a boat during spring tide, anticipating that normally at highest tidal range the highest flow velocities occur. Flow velocity was measured using an Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP). A Nortek AquaPro 600 kHz was available that can measure flow velocity in vertical layers of minimally 1 m. The ADCP measured velocity with respect to the boat every 1 s in layers of 1 m, sailing from west to east over the transect indicated in Figure 5.3. Near the ADCP flow cannot be measured. Therefore, the first depth cell was set at 1.5 m below the water surface. Near the bed, the measured flow velocity is affected by the bed. Therefore, measurements in the lowest 6% of the water column need to be ignored. The boat was sailing at low speed (1-2 m/s) in order to get highest possible

accuracy. Accounting for the boat speed, as measured by a GPS on the boat, we obtained the flow velocity in northern and eastern direction. Inherent to ADCP measurements is that noise is present in the observations. A useful result is obtained after averaging. Hence, we present width averaged flow velocity for each of the transects during the 13 hours periods of both short-term campaigns. In total 12-13 transects were sailed during the measurement period of about 12 hours.

Additionally, in that 12 hours period also salinity, temperature and pH vertical profiles were measured at 2 fixed locations near the transect, using a multiparametric probe that measured pressure, conductivity and temperature. The probe was lowered at a constant low speed. We used the measurements of the down cast to obtain profiles of salinity, temperature and pH every 0.1 m. These variables may be used to assess the source of the water and may also be used to estimate the marine litter pollution. In order to reference the observations to MSL, we have used the variations of the bed level height over time and corrected with the high and low tide water levels from harmonics. The resulting water level is an estimation and may include a systematic error, but probably it is within +/- 0.2 m. We also used this estimated water level to present the ADCP results. The results are similar for the two fixed locations. We present only the results of the fixed locations, where the water depth was largest.

5.3.2. Results

Both short-term campaigns were carried out during lower-than-average river discharge (9 and 18 m³/s, respectively). They show a strong vertical stratification, with a difference in salinity of around 25 psu (Figure 5.4 and Figure 5.5). Considering that the maximum possible difference between fresh water and sea water is about 33 psu and that the water depth at the transect location is only about 4 m, this means that the vertical density gradient is very large in comparison with other estuaries.

For the “summer” campaign, the salinity observed near the surface is in between 3-8 psu and near the bed 30-32 (Figure 5.4). The temperature of the river water in the upper layer is higher for this campaign, whereas for the winter campaign the sea water is warmer (Figure 5.5). However, for the density and associated flow variation in the water column, the temperature differences are unimportant with respect to the very large vertical variation in salinity. For the winter campaign the river discharge was two times higher than during the summer campaign, and this resulted in a lower salinity near the surface (in between 2-5 psu) than for the “summer” campaign. Also, the layer of brackish water is thicker during the winter campaign. As expected, the lowest salinity near the surface occurs around low tide for both campaigns.

The width averaged flow velocity did not exceed a magnitude of 0.5 m/s for the 1 m depth intervals for both campaigns. During the “summer” campaign, the flow velocity was low in the first part of the day and in the second part of the day flow was towards the ocean (Figure 5.4 top, where southward flow is along the channel towards the ocean). During the winter campaign flow in the middle of the water column was mostly directed northward (into the estuary), showing a maximum at around 12:00 (Figure 5.5 top). That maximum may be related to the flood tide. At 18:51 the flow in the middle of the water column was southward, which can be explained by the ebb tide. The flow near the surface in the brackish water layer was not measured unfortunately. We expect that, driven by the large vertical density differences, a net flow directed northward occurs in the salt part of the water column and a net flow southward occurs in the brackish upper layer. This estuarine circulation can explain the observed northward flow during most of the day during the winter campaign, but it does not explain the observed generally southward flow during the “summer” campaign (Figure 5.4 top). We cannot explain this southward flow with the measured data. Although the measurement error is relatively large due to the low flow velocities, still the result seems realistic, since all width averaged flow velocities are directed southward during the second part of the day.

So, we can conclude from these short-term campaigns that flow velocity magnitudes are low (width averaged at the transect it does not exceed 0.3 m/s) during the low river discharge conditions. The campaigns were carried out at spring tide. We expect that during lower tidal range for the same low river discharges the flow velocity magnitude is the same or lower than found during the tidal cycle at spring tide.

Figure 5.4 Width averaged flow velocity to the north (top; m/s), salinity (middle; psu) and temperature (bottom; °C) for the 'summer' short-term campaign. The blue lines are the estimated water level and black diamonds and lines denote the (lowest in the transect) bed level.

Figure 5.5 Width averaged flow velocity to the north (top; m/s), salinity (middle; psu) and temperature (bottom; °C) for the winter short-term campaign. The blue lines are the estimated water level and black diamonds and lines denote the (lowest in the transect) bed level.

5.4. Long-term campaigns

5.4.1. Methodology

For the long-term campaigns, instruments were deployed for several weeks (see

Table 5.1 for the periods) at two sampling points (Figure 5.3). At sampling point 1 (for the second long-term campaign 1*), two CTDs were installed: one close to the bottom and another one floating on a buoy at a constant distance to the surface (Figure 5.6). Additionally, an ADCP was mounted upward looking in a frame and lowered to the bed. At sampling point 2, one CTD at the surface and another one close to the bottom were installed, as shown in Figure 5.6. The CTD's and the ADCP measured at a time interval of 5 minutes. The observations were smoothed using a moving average with a window of 45 minutes for water level and 2 hours for salinity and temperature in order to reduce noise in the observations.

The first long-term campaign was performed in June 2022 with summer conditions. It was completed and the instruments were retrieved. However, the ADCP and lower CTD at location 1 were covered in mud and have not resulted in useful measurements. Furthermore, the first campaign was carried out with an older type of CTD, since the instruments that we intended to use could not be delivered in time. The batteries were depleted within less than two weeks.

For the second campaign a newer type of CTD instruments were used with respect to the first long-term campaign. Sampling point 1 was redefined (sampling point 1* in Figure 5.3) in order to avoid that near-bed instruments would be covered by mud. The same ADCP used for the short-term campaign was now deployed in a frame at location 1* looking upwards (Figure 5.3). The configuration of the ADCP was the same as for the short-term campaigns. The measured flow velocities were smoothed using a moving average with a window of 2 hours in order to reduce noise. All observations were successful up to 22 November, and the four CTD's have measured until around 15 December 2022 (

Table 5.1).

Figure 5.6 Schematic overview of the instruments deployment for the long-term campaign for point 1 (left) and point 2 (right)

5.4.2. Results

The first long-term campaign resulted in about two-weeks observations of water level, salinity and temperature in the water column at locations 1 and 2 (Figure 5.7). The pressure sensors lower in the water column remained at a similar level and show a realistic tidal variation of about 2 m, in agreement with the normal tidal variations in the Portuguese coast. The sensors floating on a buoy had a constant distance to the water level, and thus measured a constant pressure. As the vertical reference was going up and down with the water level, this data is not useful. The sensors fixed to the bed did have a fixed vertical reference level. At location 1 only the pressure sensor gave results, since the instrument was covered in mud. At location 2 the salinity and temperature show that at about 3 m deep the water is oceanic, whereas at the surface it varies with tides and most likely river discharge. From the hydrological model we only know that the river discharge was about $10 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ in the first four days of this campaign. This lower river discharge can result in a (very) high difference of up to 27 psu over only about 2 m vertically. This observation is in line with the very high stratification that was found during the short-term campaigns. At the moments the salinity is not clearly higher at location 2, the salinity is similar for both surface points, meaning that then the along channel salinity gradient near the water surface is limited.

Figure 5.7 Results of the first long-term campaign using four older types of CTD and with a limited duration due to battery depletion. The water level depicts the water depth above each of the sensors (so it is indicative for local water depth). The CTD at location 1 low in the water column was covered in mud, resulting in a constant salinity and temperature.

For the second long-term campaign, we obtained successful flow observations for the first three weeks (Figure 5.8, Figure 5.9 and Figure 5.10). The flow velocity magnitude at location 1* was often smaller than 0.1 m/s and was maximally 0.63 m/s (Figure 5.9). This maximum occurred during a period of about 2 days around 18 November 2022, when apparently a high river discharge occurred. The entire water column is fresh at both locations and in all ADCP bins a flow velocity towards the ocean of 0.5-0.6 m/s was recorded (Figure 5.10). The highest flow velocity magnitude occurred at 4.5 m from the ADCP (cell 4). For cells above 4.5 m, the flow was only obtained during relatively high water level. For these reasons, we show the observed flow velocity at the lowest measuring cell (or bin) at 1.5 m and for the bin at 4.5 m from the ADCP (Figure 5.9 and Figure 5.10). Generally, the flow was towards the ocean most of the time, being to the west-south-west at location 1*, corresponding to ebb flow. In the lower part of water column the direction of the flow reversed for short periods within a day, corresponding to flood tide. Near the surface, flow was always

directed to the ocean, which can be explained by the constant inflow of fresh water into the estuary upstream at the weir in combination with an estuarine circulation.

Also for this second campaign, the water level with respect to the lower sensors depicts the tidal variation realistically (Figure 5.10). Different than in the first long-term campaign, the CTD's near the surface did not remain at a constant level, probably because the mass of the newer CTD is much smaller than the older type used in the first campaign. The bed level at location 1* was substantially lower than at location 1 (the first long-term campaign). The observations started around neap tide and show a typical spring-neap variation, with the highest tidal range one week and three weeks after the start of the campaign.

The salinity in the first week shows that lower in the water column the estuary was nearly as salt as the ocean, whereas near the surface it varied much within a tidal cycle (Figure 5.10). Around spring tide (around 9 November 2022) the salinity remains relatively low near the surface for 1-2 days, whereas the variation at the lower sensors is large. During the period around 18 November 2022 when the highest flow velocity magnitude occurred, the estuary seems to be well mixed: at all four sensors the water was fresh and had a similar temperature. In this period it was neap tide, resulting in relatively vertical mixing due to tides. Therefore, the fresh water at all sensors can only be explained by a period of (very) high river discharge. Although the river discharge is not yet available, substantial precipitation was measured at stations in the region on 8 and 9 November, supporting that a relatively high river discharge occurred³.

The week after this apparent elevated river discharge, the surface layer is more or less fresh (1-3 psu) and lower in the water column the salinity is high (30-35 psu) for most of the time. It is remarkable that lower in the water column at location 1* the salinity sometimes drops to the same salinity as near the surface, while this does not occur at location 2 in this last week, although the sensor at location 1* is deeper (Figure 5.10). Apparently, the horizontal difference in salinity over only about 1 km distance is substantial, due to the fresh water input close to location 1*.

³ <https://www.ipma.pt/pt/oclima/monitoriza.dia>

Figure 5.8 All flow observations (m/s) at location 1* starting at 31 October until 22 November 2022 in eastward (upper panel) and northward direction (lower panel).

Figure 5.9 Flow velocity vectors at location 1* each 4 hours for the three weeks period at 4.5 m above the ADCP (upper panel) and at 1.5 m above the ADCP (lower panel).

Figure 5.10 Observations from the second long-term campaign starting at 31 October until 22 November 2022 using the newer type of CTD's and with flow velocity results (lower panel) at 1.5 m (bin 1) and 4.5 m from the ADCP (bin 4).

During the last weeks of the second long-term campaign only water level, salinity and temperature were monitored (Figure 5.11). An elevated river discharge seems to have occurred around 24 November 2022, also in agreement with the precipitation observed at stations in the days before and on 24 November 2022. The elevated

river discharge flushed all salt water out of the estuary. Furthermore, the salinity observations in the weeks after this second river discharge peak show that at location 1* the salinity lower in the water column increased to maximally around 20 psu, whereas it increased up to about 32 psu at location 2. Hence, during these weeks an along channel salinity gradient remained present, whereas in the first three weeks the salinity at both these sensors increased to a similar level (Figure 5.10). Again, in order to find an explanation for this difference in horizontal gradient and what this implies for the flow velocity in the estuary, we need to know the actual river discharge.

Figure 5.11 Results of the last weeks of the second long-term campaign (19-22 November 2022 is overlapping with Figure 5.10), showing a few days when the water was fresh at all four sensors (middle panel).

5.5. Hydrological model

5.5.1. Wflow model set-up

In order to obtain insight in the temporal variation of the river discharge over time, we set-up a hydrological model of the Ave River basin, which has an area of approximately 1390 km². We used a grid-based hydrological modelling platform developed by Deltares: Wflow. It allows users to account for precipitation, interception, snow accumulation and melt, evapotranspiration, soil water, surface water and groundwater recharge in a fully distributed environment (Figure 5.12). Wflow includes a number of hydrological modules. For MAELSTROM, the physics-based SBM concept was chosen, as it is targeted to perform hydrological simulations using GIS raster data based on global (European) datasets, which makes it the concept of choice in data scarce environments. Based on gridded topography, soil, land use and climate data, Wflow SBM calculates all hydrological fluxes at any given point in the model at a given time step. The movement of surface water across the landscape is determined by the reservoir and kinematic wave modules providing more accurate representation of river discharges.

Figure 5.12 Overview of the main hydrological processes in the Wflow SBM model

A Wflow model (hydrology) requires three main types of inputs:

- **Model construction dataset**, such as a Digital Elevation Model (DEM), soil type, land use and stream network and the parameters derived from them (such as slope, soil hydraulic conductivity, rooting depth, surface roughness, etc.).
- **Model forcing dataset**, such as precipitation, potential evapotranspiration and temperature.
- **Model calibration and validation dataset** such as discharge and rainfall timeseries.

As forcing data, Wflow SBM requires three main meteorological variables, to be defined per computational grid cell per time step: total precipitation (in mm), average air temperature (in °C) and potential evapotranspiration (in mm). In this study, the meteorological data, precipitation and air temperature, were derived from the European **E-OBS** dataset (Cornes et al., 2018). E-OBS provides daily gridded observations of different land climate variables, from 1950 to within six months of real time, at a resolution of 0.1° (~9km). Potential evaporation was not directly available in E-OBS, and was computed from air temperature, pressure, and incoming shortwave radiation, using the Makkink equation. Since the precipitation data is essential, the E-OBS rainfall data was validated with other precipitation data sources (annex A). After selection and validation of the precipitation data, the hydrological model is calibrated (annex A.4).

5.5.2. Resulting river discharge

In order to provide discharge timeseries as input to the hydrodynamic model of the estuary, the modelled river discharge was extracted at the outlet (LAT 41.34, LON -8.75) for a year from June 2020 to July 2022 (current end of the E-OBS dataset). The discharge timeseries in 2021 shows a peak in February of around 300 m³/s, which may seem a bit high (Figure 5.13). Looking back at the available observed discharge (summing the values of both the Ave and Este River at Ponte Junqueira), it seems that such events indeed regularly appear for the Ave river (around every 3 years) between 1979 and 1990 (Figure 5.14). In the 1990s, the observed data have missing values during the high flow period. As an extra check, we looked back at the European Flood monitoring and forecasting reports: warnings were issued at these particular dates for flood risk in the Ave and surrounding rivers (Figure 5.15).

Figure 5.13 Modelled discharge (m^3/s) at the estuary of the Ave river with the days of the two short-term campaigns indicated by 'x'.

Figure 5.14 Estimation of observed discharge (m^3/s) from 1979 to 2000 summing values observed at Ponte Junqueira with either Acude de Tougues or Ponte Ave and comparison with calibrated Wflow results.

Figure 5.15 Screenshot of EFAS system⁴ with issued flash floods warning on the 10th of February 2021

5.6. Hydrodynamic model

5.6.1. Software and grid

The hydrodynamic numerical model for the Ave estuary was implemented using D-Flow Flexible Mesh (D-Flow FM), which is the hydrodynamic module of the Delft3D Flexible Mesh Suite developed by Deltares⁵. D-Flow FM is specially designed for coastal, river and estuarine areas. This hydrodynamic module calculates non-steady flow and transport phenomena that result from tidal and meteorological forcing on structured and unstructured boundary fitted grids. The term Flexible Mesh in the name refers to the flexible combination of unstructured grids, which are extremely useful to represent the dynamics of study cases that present complex geometries. Some of the areas of application of the D-Flow FM module are tide-driven flows, river discharge effects, freshwater river discharge and salt intrusion. To represent all these phenomena, the module is able to consider tidal forcing, Coriolis force, density driven flows, advection-diffusion, turbulence, time varying sources and sinks.

An unstructured grid was set-up for the Ave estuary and the surrounding coastal and oceanic zone. The grid resolution is 15 m inside the estuary and around 1 km at the oceanic western boundary. The bathymetry for the numerical grid that was obtained from several databases using MSL as vertical reference level:

⁴ https://www.efas.eu/efas_frontend/#/home

⁵ <https://oss.deltares.nl/web/delft3dfm>

- Oceanic zone: Bathymetry extracted from EMODNET 2020 (114 m resolution)⁶.
- Coastal zone: Bathymetry and topography extracted from National LiDAR 2011 (2 m resolution)⁷.
- Estuarine zone:
 - Topography extracted from the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) measured by CIIMAR researchers in 2019 using an aircraft flight (0.5 m resolution).
 - Bathymetry measured during the MAELSTROM bathymetric campaign (September 2021; Figure 5.1 right).

All the data was carefully merged to avoid inconsistencies between the different databases, using the coordinate system PT-TM06/ETRS89. Figure 5.16 shows the final topo-bathymetric data projected on the numerical grid.

Figure 5.16 The numerical grid with the bathymetry (m with respect to MSL) shown as color.

⁶ <https://www.emodnet-bathymetry.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.dgterritorio.gov.pt/cartografia/topografica/modelos-digitais-do-terreno>

5.6.2. Set-up

The first numerical modelling simulations were performed as depth averaged (2DH) to find the boundary conditions for the river discharge and the water level (tides) that result in realistic dynamics inside the estuary. The tidal forcing at the oceanic boundary was extracted from the TPXO9-atlas, with a 1/30 degrees' resolution using the TMD model (Egbert and Erofeeva, 2002). Initially, the tidal forcing was extracted for a single point and include in the entire oceanic boundary. Then, the tidal forcing was extracted at several points separated a distance of about 3 km along the model boundary, allowing a better description of the tidal behaviour inside the numerical domain.

The river discharge was forced at the river entrance just downstream of the weir. The flow was equally distributed over the cross section. Corresponding to the October 2021 short-term campaign, a constant river discharge of 9 m³/s was used. The temperature and salinity values of the oceanic and river water masses were extracted from the *in situ* data measured. For the October 2021 simulation, the riverine water was included in the numerical model with 0 psu and 19.5 °C, and the oceanic water with 36 psu and 16.5 °C. For the January 2022 simulation, the freshwater was included with 0 psu and 11.5 °C and the oceanic water with 36 psu and 13 °C. No meteorological forcing like rainfall, solar radiation or wind was considered in this model.

The initial conditions of the numerical model for the temperature and salinity were selected with the same values as the oceanic conditions. For the hydraulic roughness a Manning coefficient of 0.033 m^{1/3}/s was used, and the horizontal eddy viscosity and diffusivity were set at 1 m²/s. At the nodes surrounding the oceanic boundary, a higher horizontal eddy viscosity coefficient of 500 m²/s was included to ensure smooth entrance of the oceanic conditions and to avoid artificial hydrodynamic structures. Furthermore, to estimate the highest flow velocities that can occur in the estuary, we did another simulation with the same settings, except that river discharge was now 300 m³/s, being the highest river discharge from the hydrological model (Figure 5.13).

The 3D model was constructed from the depth averaged model, using the same conditions uniform over the depth as for the depth averaged model. Several configurations were tested, including different Manning and horizontal and vertical eddy viscosity and diffusivity coefficients, and different numbers of sigma and Z vertical layers (10, 20 and 40). For sigma layers the water depth was divided into layers with equal thickness. Hence, the thickness of the layers varies with the water depth, whereas for Z-layers the layer thickness is fixed over time and space. Moreover,

different methodologies to force the entrance of the flow at the river boundary were tested, including one or several point sources, polygons in which the river discharge was released in the upper layer and an additional channel at the river boundary.

Considering the obtained results and the computational time, the best configuration was the one using 20 sigma layers, a Manning coefficient of $0.033 \text{ s}^{1/3}/\text{m}$, a horizontal eddy viscosity and diffusivity of $1 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ and a background vertical eddy viscosity and background diffusivity of $5 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$. At the upstream boundary, a constant river discharge of $9 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ was imposed, having the same flow velocity over the cross section. The performed simulation aimed to reproduce the October 2021 short-term campaign, which presented a strong stratification (Figure 5.5). The duration of the simulations is four days, which seems long enough for the spin-up needed for this relatively small estuary (about 0.5 days).

5.6.3. Verification water level variation

A period from 26/06/2022 to 15/07/2022 was simulated using the 2DH model to extract the tidal harmonics and compare them with the tidal harmonics extracted from the water level measured by the bottom probes during June/July 2022 long-term campaign. To extract the tidal harmonics from both time series, the T-Tide Harmonic Analysis Matlab toolbox was used (Pawlowicz et al., 2002). For this simulation, and since the hydrological model data was not yet available for July 2022, a constant river discharge of $10 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ was used in order to represent low river discharge conditions during summer.

The results of the tidal harmonics for the main constituents for the long simulation (June/July 2022) are presented in Table 5.2 and Table 5.3. The comparison between the tidal constituents' amplitude and phase obtained from measured and modelled water levels revealed that the numerical model was able to reproduce the main components with satisfactory results, acknowledging that in reality the water level may also vary due to varying river discharge. The calculation of the tidal form factor (F), which is the ratio between the sum of the amplitudes of the diurnal components (K1 and O1), and the sum of the amplitudes of the semidiurnal components (S2 and M2), revealed similar values for the observed and the modelled data, indicating a semidiurnal tidal behaviour (F: 0 - 0.25 semidiurnal; F: 0.25 - 1.5 mixed, mainly semidiurnal; F: 1.5 - 3 mixed, mainly diurnal; F: > 3 diurnal).

Furthermore, the water level behaviour inside the numerical domain at the oceanic region was compared with the tidal predictions of the TMD tool (Egbert and Erofeeva,

2002) at several points. It demonstrated that the tidal propagation inside the computational domain was satisfactory.

Table 5.2: Amplitude and phase obtained from measured and modelled water levels at the upstream location for main tidal constituents (Point 1, Figure 5.3)

Tidal constituent	From measured water levels		From modelled water levels	
	Amplitude (m)	Phase (°)	Amplitude (m)	Phase (°)
O1	0.06	22.3	0.06	217.1
K1	0.1	288.5	0.11	131.0
M2	1.03	12.8	1.01	37.9
S2	0.24	229.9	0.28	264.8
	F = 0.12		F = 0.13	

Table 5.3: Amplitude and phase obtained from measured and modelled water levels at the downstream location for main tidal constituents (Point 2, Figure 5.3)

Tidal constituent	From measured water levels		From modelled water levels	
	Amplitude (m)	Phase (°)	Amplitude (m)	Phase (°)
O1	0.05	13.7	0.06	216.4
K1	0.09	312.1	0.11	130.9
M2	0.95	22.5	1.01	37.8
S2	0.19	265.6	0.27	265.1
	F = 0.13		F = 0.13	

5.6.4. Results October 2021 campaign

The 3D model simulation aiming to reproduce the October 2021 short-term campaign revealed a stratification due to the presence of both fresh riverine water from the constant river discharge and saline oceanic water. We only show results of the last day of the simulation, ensuring that the result was not determined by the initial conditions (sufficient long spin-up period). Figure 5.17 shows the salinity along the centre of the estuary (thalweg) for the last moment of high and low tide and mid-ebb and mid-flood of the performed simulation. It can be seen that the oceanic water (35 psu) is able to enter the lower part of in the estuarine region as a salt wedge. At high tide salt has intruded furthest, resulting in maximum salinity values of 10 or 15 psu next to the bottom near the river boundary (weir, left in Figure 5.17). During low tide, the salt wedge is restricted to the mouth of the estuary, and the salinity in the upper 0.5 km of the estuary is less than 5 psu in the entire water column. As expected, for all the tidal moments it is possible to see a smaller salinity near the water surface than lower in the water column.

Figure 5.19 shows the salinity in the cross-section of the estuary, where the transects were sailed. The model results show stratification, although it is not so strong as observed (Figure 5.4). Compared with the observations, Figure 5.17 and Figure 5.19 show that the model revealed a higher stratification during high tide and mid-flood conditions, although the difference in the salinity values between the surface and the bottom layer is smaller for the numerical model (around 15 psu) than for the measurements (25 psu). The numerical model presents difficulties in reproducing the stratification during low tide and mid-ebb conditions, when the oceanic water is being flushed out of the estuary. During low tide conditions, the numerical model shows more mixing than at the particular tidal cycle when observations were carried out. The same behaviour was observed for the temperature (not shown). None of the multiple solutions tested during this work was able to properly reproduce the observed stratification during low tide conditions. An explanation for the different stratification may be related to the constant river discharge we imposed, whereas in reality it varied.

Figure 5.18 shows flow velocity along the thalweg in the estuary for this specific low river discharge. The highest velocities can be found near the surface (the top layer of the model) with flow velocities towards the ocean up to maximally 0.5 m/s. Particularly, for mid-ebb conditions, it can be seen that the higher velocities are also located in the lower estuary between 1.5 km and 2.0 km (the estuary mouth), which can be explained with the narrowing of the estuary. Lower in the water column, the flow velocity can have an opposite direction with respect to flow velocity at the surface, presenting an inward (to the land) water masses movement with values up to around -0.3 m/s. A substantial inward flow was not found for mid-ebb, when the entire water column seems to be flushed from the estuarine region. At all other three moments an estuarine circulation is visible in part of the estuary, having positive (outward) velocities at the surface and inward flow lower in the water column. Figure 5.20 shows the flow velocity magnitude at the transect in the estuary, where the short-term campaigns were carried out. The flow velocity magnitude at four moments is in the same order as observed in part of the cross-section (upper panel in Figure 5.4).

Figure 5.17 Vertical profiles of salinity along the thalweg for the simulation aiming to reproduce the October 2021 short-term campaign.

Figure 5.18 Vertical profiles of flow velocity towards the ocean along the thalweg from the simulation aiming to reproduce the October 2021 short-term campaign.

Figure 5.19 Salinity at the transect from the simulation aiming to reproduce the October 2021 campaign.

Figure 5.20 Flow velocity magnitude at the transect from the simulation aiming to reproduce the October 2021 campaign.

5.6.5. Maximal flow velocity maps

For the design and functioning of the Bubble Barrier system it is important to know the maximal flow velocity that may occur. At the moment with the highest flow velocity (high tide) for the constant low river discharge simulation, Figure 5.21 shows the velocity map for the entire estuary. Only the top layer is shown, since the flow velocity magnitude in lower layers is smaller. The normal range within the middle and lower part of the water column is -0.2 to 0.2 m/s (Figure 5.18 for the thalweg). The y-coordinate for the region selected to implement the Bubble Barrier system is in between 186.2 and 186.7 km. Figure 5.21 shows that for the low river discharge during the October 2021 campaign the highest flow velocities (0.5 m/s) occur south of the region selected for implementation of the Bubble Barrier system.

Figure 5.22 shows the flow velocity maps for the low river discharge for the top layer at the four moments for the region where the Bubble Barrier system is expected to be implemented (Figure 3.2). The flow velocity near the surface always points in the direction of the ocean for all the four moments. As expected, the higher values were obtained in the central deepest part of the estuary (the navigation channel). The highest flow velocity magnitudes in the top layer were obtained for high tide conditions, and the lowest for low tide conditions. So, the flow velocity magnitudes for this low river discharge simulation did not exceed the limit of 0.5-0.7 m/s that is used for Bubble Barrier systems in rivers.

Figure 5.23 shows the depth averaged flow velocity maps for the highest river discharge obtained for the considered 2 years period of 300 m³/s (note the difference in colour scale with respect to Figure 5.22). At this extreme river discharge, it can be assumed that the entire estuary is mixed and fresh, and the maximal flow velocity can be determined from the depth averaged flow velocity. Using the depth averaged model, the highest magnitude was calculated to be 1.6 m/s at some locations in the selected region (Figure 5.23). Assuming a logarithmic velocity profile, the maximal flow velocity at a vertical level may be maximally 1.2 times higher than the calculated depth averaged flow velocity. Hence, the maximal flow velocity at a point in water column can be maximally 1.9 m/s. This highest flow velocity magnitude occurs around low tide, as expected due to the high water surface level gradient along the estuary for that moment. Usually the highest flow velocity occurs near the water surface. The direction of the depth averaged flow velocity is always towards the ocean for this extreme river discharge (Figure 5.23).

Figure 5.21 Map of near-surface flow velocity vectors and magnitude (colour) for the entire estuarine region during high tide conditions.

Figure 5.22 Maps of near-surface flow velocity vectors and magnitude (colour) for the estuarine region selected for the implementation of the Bubble Barrier system (Figure 3.2) for a river discharge of $9 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$.

Figure 5.23 Maps of depth averaged flow velocity vectors and magnitude (colour, please note the difference in scale with respect to Figure 5.22) for an extreme river discharge of $300 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$.

5.7. Discussion

5.7.1. Maximal flow velocity magnitude

The tides mainly determine the maximal flow velocity at low river discharge. At mean and high river discharge we have limited observations. However, a period was observed when the river discharge was sufficient high to flush the salt out of the estuary, and a peak flow velocity magnitude at one location was observed of 0.63 m/s (Figure 5.10). Since we do not know the river discharge in that period, we were not able to simulate this period with the hydrodynamic model and obtain the flow velocity variation in space and time. Anyhow, this one observation shows that at high river discharge the maximal flow velocity can be within the range for the limit 0.5-0.7 m/s occasionally. Still, for the largest part of the tidal cycle, the magnitude may not exceed this range.

During an extreme river discharge of 300 m³/s (Figure 5.13) we show that the maximal depth averaged flow velocity magnitude is 1.6 m/s (Figure 5.23) and that the highest flow velocity that occurred in the water column may have been maximally 1.9 m/s. This estimate of the peak flow velocity during an extreme river discharge may be considered for the design of the Bubble Barrier system, and may be especially relevant for the mooring of the catchment system. For the functioning of the Bubble Barrier system, mean and low river discharges may be most relevant, since they occur most of the time.

At low river discharge, the peak flow velocity magnitude in time and space was found to be 0.5 m/s. Due to the upstream weir, the length of the estuary is limited to 2 km. The volume of water that enters the estuary during flood is limited with respect to other estuaries, explaining the limited magnitude. In the short-term campaigns, the highest width averaged observed flow velocity in the middle of the water column was 0.3 m/s. This is in agreement with the velocity values obtained with the 3D hydrodynamic model. As a result of those low velocities during low river discharge conditions, the mixing of the water column is limited and a very strong vertical stratification can occur, as it was observed. Hence, the Ave estuary can be classified as a salt wedge estuary, showing a sharp transition from salt sea water to brackish-fresh river water for low river discharge conditions. During the short-term campaigns carried out at low river discharge, the difference in salinity near the surface and about 4 m deeper near the bed was around 25 psu, which is very high with respect to other estuaries. The long-term campaigns confirmed this difference for the summer observations, with variations of 27 psu over 2 m vertically. However, the numerical

model was not able to perfectly reproduce this stratification. During high tide conditions a difference of 15 psu was represented. In other shallow estuaries such differences as the ones measured in the Ave estuary are rarely found.

5.7.2. Litter transport and accumulation

At the same days of the short-term campaigns (i.e. during low river discharge), floating litter items were visually monitored. On 19 October 2021 and on 17 January 2022 19.1 and 16.3 floating items per hour were recorded in the estuary, respectively (MAELSTROM D2.3). Most of these items seemed to be land-based. With the limited wind during these days, this floating litter was likely to be transported with the flow near the surface in the fresh-brackish water layer near the water surface. Although we were not able to monitor flow in this layer, we expect that the flow towards the ocean in this upper layer was substantially higher than in the situation that the river discharge was transported to the ocean in the whole cross section (as in a river). The simulation with the 3D numerical model for low river discharge confirmed that an estuarine circulation can occur in a large part of the estuary (Figure 5.18 and Figure 5.21). Within half a tidal cycle a litter item can be transported from the weir to the ocean via the upper layer. Hence, for floating litter, the strong stratification can accelerate transport of litter towards the ocean. Plastic litter suspended in the water column, however, may show landward flow at times that the flow in the upper layer is towards the ocean depending on its position in the water column. It is not straightforward to obtain its net transport and its trajectory in the estuary, due to the strong stratification and associated flow velocity variation in the vertical.

The flow velocity map for low river discharge can also be used to find regions where it is likely that the flow velocity magnitude is normally small (blue in Figure 5.21). In these regions, deposition of sinking litter and possibly accumulation of floating marine litter may occur. These regions include zones close to the estuary margins in the upper estuary, west of the thalweg in the middle estuary (around -51.1, 186 km) and a zone east of the thalweg in the lower estuary (around -51.3, 185.6 km). However, it must be noticed that the western estuarine margin in the upper and middle estuarine region is an artificial rock wall, limiting the accumulation of marine litter. The latter two zones are in agreement with the sites of sediment accumulation. The small bay in the right margin of the estuarine mouth (around -51.1, 186 km) is an artificially semi-enclosed area for the shipyard, which can also be a source of litter. So, litter found in this area may either be littered locally or may be originating from the estuary (river).

6. Conclusion

6.1. Venice coastal area

Based on existing hydrodynamic model results for the Adriatic Sea over a period of 11 months, we calculated the transport and fate of marine litter assuming a constant sinking velocity. The source input was estimated for marine litter from cities, from rivers and from aquaculture and fisheries. Despite the various uncertainties in the modelling methods, the resulting maps of the item density on the sea floor represent a first assessment on the distribution of marine macrolitter accumulation in this region. A potential hotspot map for each of the three sources was obtained by showing locations above the threshold of 75 particles/m². Although these potential hotspots need to be verified quantitatively by in situ measurements in order to assess the robustness of the approach and of the model performance, the cable robot is likely to be able to remove relatively high amounts of litter at the potential hotspots.

Considering the three main sources, we conclude at the scale of the Adriatic Sea that:

- A. Hotspots are connected to the sources.
- B. Marine litter from cities resulted in the largest number of hotspots, followed by the river hotspots.
- C. The aquaculture hotspots are mostly located in the Northern Adriatic, near the Venice coastal area.

Considering the Venice coastal areas, we conclude that:

- D. One large seabed hotspot was identified in front of the most southern inlet of the Venice lagoon.
- E. Overall, the river source simulations produce more hotspots, located further offshore.
- F. From the city sources, a large area in the Venice lagoon is indicated as potential hotspot.

6.2. Ave estuary

For the Ave estuary, being about 2 km in length from a weir to the Atlantic Ocean, and based on the field observations and on the numerical model simulations, we conclude that:

- A. The flow is mainly determined by the tides and the river discharge, and the effect of wind on the flow is limited.
- B. During low river discharge conditions, the estuary is likely to be highly stratified, meaning that a fresh-brackish water layer is on top of oceanic water. The flow

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- velocity magnitude in every layer does not exceed 0.5 m/s in the area selected to implement the Bubble Barrier system. The highest flow velocities occur near the water surface.
- C. At relatively high river discharge, salt water was flushed out of the estuary, and the entire water column was fresh. Considering an extreme river discharge of 300 m³/s, the maximal flow velocity magnitude that can occur at a point in the cross section is 1.9 m/s.
 - D. During low river discharge, floating marine litter transport to the ocean is accelerated by the estuarine circulation, since the flow velocity near the surface is directed towards the ocean for most of the tidal cycle and only changes direction in lower layers. Some low velocity regions were found at the surface, which can indicate possible hotspots for marine litter accumulation.
 - E. During high river discharge, the entire water column is more mixed, and the transport is mainly outwards. For this condition, it is expected that the marine litter could be transported efficiently to the ocean at all water depths.

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A. ANNEX Hydrological model Ave River basin

A.1 Ave basin hydrometrical stations

Due to the lack of data available for the Ave River basin, the hydrological model was developed to force the hydrodynamic model with accurate estimation of river discharge, allowing the calibration and validation of the hydrodynamic results. The hydrological model was forced with several hydrometric stations available along the Ave river basin (Figure A.1, Table A.1).

Figure A.1 Hydrometrical stations selected to construct the Ave River hydrological model (Source: SNIRH).

Table A.1 Details of the hydrometrical stations.

Station Code	Name station	River	Lat.	Lon.	River discharge data
05E/02AE	Açude de Tougues	Ave	41.368	-8.698	Daily mean from 01/10/1978 - 30/09/1989 (with gaps)
05E/03H	Ponte Ave	Ave	41.351	-8.681	Daily mean from 01/10/1984 - 31/10/2000 (with gaps)
05E/01H	Ponte Junqueira	Este (tributary)	41.389	-8.689	Daily mean from 01/10/1978 - 10/12/2000 (with gaps)
05G/01H	Ponte Brandão	Selho (tributary)	41.414	-8.368	Daily mean from 01/10/1978 - 09/02/2015 (with gaps)
04H/01H	Garfe	Ave	41.542	-8.249	Daily mean from 01/10/1986 - 30/03/2009 (with gaps)
04I/01A	Albufeira de Guilhofrei (R.E.)	Ave	41.585	-8.138	Daily mean from 09/04/2017 to 28/07/2017

A.2 Detailed set-up

A first setup of the Ave catchment model was prepared using open access data sources. The model catchment properties and construction datasets are:

- The global 3 arc second (~90 meters) MERIT Hydro Adjusted Elevations dataset (Yamazaki et al., 2019) for model elevation and associated topological information (such as catchment delineation, 1D flow direction, slope, stream network and stream characteristics).
- The global 250 meters SoilGrids Database (Hengl et al., 2017) for soil properties (clay, silt, and organic carbon content as well as bulk density) and derived Wflow model soil parameters (such as hydraulic conductivity, porosity, soil water content and saturation content...).
- The European 100 meters Corine Land Cover (CLC) 2018 land cover map from the European Environment Agency for land-use, land-cover classes and associated vegetation parameters (such as surface roughness, rotting depth of the vegetation, fraction of paved areas etc.).

To prepare the Wflow model maps and parameters from these datasets, we utilised HydroMT model builder (Deltares, 2021), which is a Python toolbox that collects and prepares the data in a ready-to-use format. HydroMT also makes use of state-of-the-art parameter estimation techniques and (pedo)-transfer functions to limit calibration effort. These (pedo)-transfer functions are using different datasets (e.g., clay content of the soil, sand content of the soil, etc.) to combine into model parameter values (e.g., vertical hydraulic conductivity of the topsoil) based on experience from different models around the world (Imhoff et al., 2020).

The Ave hydrological model was setup in LAT/LON coordinates to optimally make use of available global open datasets. The model coordinates are in WGS84 (EPSG:4326) and the model resolution is 1/120 degrees (approximately 1000 meters). **Figure A.2** shows the Wflow model schematization and boundaries for the Ave River basin as well as some of its main catchment characteristics.

Figure A.2 Wflow model for the Ave River basin: elevation (a), land cover (b) and soil properties (c).

A.3 Selection of rainfall data and datasets

Rainfall data quality is crucial for hydrological modelling and therefore a second dataset was chosen: the global **ERA5-Reanalysis** dataset (C3S, 2017). ERA5 provides global hourly estimates of different atmospheric, land and oceanic climate variables, from 1979 to within three months of real time, at a resolution of 0.25° (~25km). Using two different datasets allows to test the sensitivity of the Wflow model to the rainfall inputs and to distinguish during the calibration phase if the potentially poor model performances originate from poor rainfall data or poor model parameters values.

Furthermore, to validate both the rainfall grids from the global datasets and to calibrate and validate the modelled discharge values from the Wflow model, observed rainfall and discharge timeseries are crucial. Such timeseries were received from the SNIRH portal for different locations in the basins at daily timesteps (Figure A.3). Observed precipitation was received for 18 stations in the basins from 1931 to 2021. Discharge timeseries were scarce and available for 5 stations for older decades (around 1980 to 2000) with data gaps in between (two stations had data for recent decades, Ponte Brandão until 2015 and Garfe until 2009).

Table A.2 summarizes all the different global and local datasets used to prepare the model.

Figure A.3 Available observed rainfall (top) and discharge (bottom) timeseries locations.

Table A.2 Overview of the different datasets used by the Wflow SBM model for the Ave River

Static data	
Digital elevation model (DEM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global 3 arc second (~90 meters) MERIT Hydro Adjusted Elevations dataset (Yamazaki et al., 2019)
Land use classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Corine Land Cover (CLC) 2018, Version 2020_20u1 (European Environment Agency)
Soil properties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global 250 meters SoilGrids Database (Hengl et al., 2017)
Dynamic data	
Precipitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global ERA5-Reanalysis dataset (C3S, 2017) European E-OBS dataset (Cornes et al., 2018)
Temperature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global ERA5-Reanalysis dataset (C3S, 2017) European E-OBS dataset (Cornes et al., 2018)
Downwards and incident solar radiation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global ERA5-Reanalysis dataset (C3S, 2017) European E-OBS dataset (Cornes et al., 2018)
Atmospheric pressure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global ERA5-Reanalysis dataset (C3S, 2017) European E-OBS dataset (Cornes et al., 2018)
Calibration/validation data	
Rainfall timeseries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Observations from SNIRH
Discharge timeseries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Observations from SNIRH

The first part of the calibration/validation consists of analysing the quality of the gridded rainfall data from E-OBS and ERA5 compared to the observed timeseries at different locations in the basin. Figure A.4 to Figure A.6 show the comparison between observations and the global data for different locations (the analysis and selection are based on results for all available 18 stations). Comparison was performed between 1980 (start of the global data) and 2000, for which discharge observations are also available for all stations. In this period 12 stations had sufficient data coverage (few to no missing values). From the analysis on rainfall volumes, there is no clear conclusion on which dataset is better than the other. In most cases, ERA5 seems to better estimates the yearly volumes (Figure A.4) but with a tendency to overestimate and without a good distribution of the rain volumes per month. E-OBS seems to generally underestimate the rainfall volumes per year, but seems to have a much better distribution of these volumes per month especially during the dry season (Figure A.5 and

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Figure A.6). For some stations E-OBS estimates better the yearly volumes than ERA5 and for a few locations, the quality of the gridded rainfall datasets seems poor (Figure A.6). For the next phase of the calibration, the hydrological model was then run with both datasets and the selection was based on which dataset seem to catch better the high flow events.

Figure A.4 Rainfall comparison between observations, E-OBS (blue) and ERA5 (green) for Escudeiros station. From top to bottom: total rainfall per year [mm/yr], average rainfall per month [mm/month], and cumulative rainfall volumes from 1980 to 2000 [mm].

Figure A.5 Rainfall comparison between observations, E-OBS (blue) and ERA5 (green) for Brancelhe station. From top to bottom: total rainfall per year [mm/yr], average rainfall per month [mm/month], and cumulative rainfall volumes from 1980 to 2000 [mm].

Figure A.6 Rainfall comparison between observations, E-OBS (blue) and ERA5 (green) for Parada station. From top to bottom: total rainfall per year [mm/yr], average rainfall per month [mm/month], and cumulative rainfall volumes from 1980 to 2000 [mm].

A.4 Calibration and validation

The model was first run with a set of default values obtained from the HydroMT Modelbuilder with both rainfall from ERA5 and E-OBS. Figure A.7, Figure A.8 and Figure A.9 show the observed and modelled discharge and cumulative discharge timeseries with E-OBS or ERA5 precipitation as input. From these figures, we can see that E-OBS seems better suited for use with the hydrological model as the discharge volumes are well represented for most stations (Acude de Tougues, Ponte Ave, Ponte Brandao and Ponte Junqueira). In addition, ERA5 seems to overestimate most of the peak rainfall and introduce additional intermediate ones, compared to E-OBS. For Garfe station (Figure A.9), both gridded rainfall seem to perform similarly but missed the main peak in 1989 probably as this is a station in a small tributary with a small upstream catchment, prone to very local events (which are easily missed by gridded dataset with a low spatial resolution). From this analysis, it seems that the E-OBS dataset is better suited for the study of the Ave River as the peak flows and low flows conditions are better represented and it selected for the second step of model calibration.

Figure A.7 Simulated (top) and cumulative (bottom) observed and modelled discharge using precipitation from E-OBS (blue) or ERA5 (green) at Ponte Brandao station.

Figure A.8 Simulated (top) and cumulative (bottom) observed and modelled discharge using precipitation from E-OBS (blue) or ERA5 (green) at Ponte Ave station

Figure A.9 Simulated (top) and cumulative (bottom) observed and modelled discharge using precipitation from E-OBS (blue) or ERA5 (green) at Garfe station

In the second step, a few hydrological model parameters were changed one by one to perform a sensitivity analysis of the model, before being combined during calibration. From experience and other studies (Imhoff et al., 2020), the model parameters that were analysed are:

- Soil: the vertical hydraulic conductivity at the soil surface **KsatVer**
- Soil: the horizontal hydraulic conductivity at the soil surface **KsatHorFrac** (multiplier of the vertical hydraulic conductivity KsatVer)
- Soil: the scaling parameter **f** that controls the exponential decline of conductivity with soil depth
- Soil: the saturated water content (porosity) of the soil **θ_s**
- Vegetation/evaporation: the rooting depth of vegetation **RootingDepth**

The selection of the best parameter set for the Ave river was based on several criteria:

- Visual inspection of the hydrograph
- Best representation of the (annual) cumulative discharge (volume)

- Computation of efficiency coefficients: NSE (Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency) and KGE (Kling-Gupta Efficiency). These coefficients vary between $-\infty$ (very poor) and 1 (perfect). It is considered that a model starts to be acceptable at 0.4, good at 0.6 and very good from 0.8. KGE is an adapted version of NSE focusing a little less on discharge peaks and more on the water volumes (both high and low flow periods are considered).

Figure A.10 shows an example of the sensitivity analysis of Wflow parameters at Ponte Junqueira in 1985. From the analysis, KsatHorFrac seems to have the most influence and RootingDepth the least. For the calibration phase, combination of KsatHorFrac and its linked parameter f as well as θ_s were run. Values and combination of the parameters were chosen in order to increase the baseflow and reduce the peak flow values. Figure A.11 shows the results of certain parameter combination at the same station.

Figure A.10 Sensitivity analysis of Wflow model parameters at Ponte Junqueira in 1985

Figure A.11 Calibration of Wflow parameters at Ponte Junqueira in 1985

From the different selection criteria and looking at the different stations available (Figure A.3), the final parameter values retained are:

- KsatHorFrac: 500 [-]
- f: multiplier of 0.5 compared to the values obtained from HydroMT and the pedo-transfer functions
- θ_s : multiplier of 1.2 compared to the values obtained from HydroMT and the pedo-transfer functions
- Other parameters: default values obtained from HydroMT